

The seal of the University of Bologna is a large, circular emblem in the background. It features a central figure, likely a saint or scholar, surrounded by various scenes and text. The outer ring contains the Latin text "UNIVERSITAS BOLOGNENSIS" and "S. PETRI UBIQUE PATRIS". The inner ring contains "COLL. IUR. POSTI.", "COLL. MED. ET ART.", and "COLL. IUR. CIVIL.". The seal is rendered in a light, golden-brown color.

**On the Quality-Based Evaluation and Selection of
Grid Services (Ph.D. Thesis)**

Sergio Andreozzi

Technical Report UBLCS-2006-2

March 2006

Department of Computer Science
University of Bologna
Mura Anteo Zamboni 7
40127 Bologna (Italy)

The University of Bologna Department of Computer Science Research Technical Reports are available in PDF and gzipped PostScript formats via anonymous FTP from the area `ftp.cs.unibo.it:/pub/TR/UBLCS` or via WWW at URL `http://www.cs.unibo.it/`. Plain-text abstracts organized by year are available in the directory ABSTRACTS.

Note added in 2026 archival deposit. Defense date: 27 April 2006. The FTP and HTTP URLs above are no longer publicly accessible. The UBLCS Technical Report series was not migrated to the University of Bologna's institutional repositories (AMS Acta, AMS Dottorato). A 2007 snapshot of the UBLCS directory listing is preserved at the Wayback Machine: <https://web.archive.org/web/20071102222857/http://www.cs.unibo.it/pub/TR/UBLCS/>. This thesis is deposited for open access at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19698772> (concept DOI, Zenodo, 2026), licensed under the Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License (CC BY 4.0).

Recent Titles from the UBLCS Technical Report Series

- 2005-3 On some combinatorial optimization problems arising from computer networks (Ph.D. Thesis), Vassura, M., March 2005.
- 2005-4 Experiences with Synthetic Network Emulation for Complex IP based Networks (Ph.D. Thesis), Cacciaguerra, S., March 2005.
- 2005-5 Interactivity Maintenance for Event Synchronization in Massive Multiplayer Online Games (Ph.D. Thesis), Ferretti, S., March 2005.
- 2005-6 Reasoning with preferences over temporal, uncertain, and conditional statements (Ph.D. Thesis), Venable, K. B., March 2005.
- 2005-7 Whole Platform (Ph.D. Thesis), Solmi, R., March 2005.
- 2005-8 Loss Functions and Structured Domains for Support Vector Machines (Ph.D. Thesis), Portera, F., March 2005.
- 2005-9 A Reasoning Infrastructure to Support Cooperation of Intelligent Agents on the Semantic Grid, Dragoni, N., Gaspari, M., Guidi, D., April 2005.
- 2005-10 Fault Tolerant Knowledge Level Communication in Open Asynchronous Multi-Agent Systems, Dragoni, N., Gaspari, M., April 2005.
- 2005-11 The AEDSS Application Ontology: Enhanced Automatic Assessment of EDSS in Multiple Sclerosis, Gaspari, M., Saletti, N., Scandellari, C., Stecchi, S., April 2005.
- 2005-12 How to cheat BitTorrent and why nobody does, Hales, D., Patarin, S., May 2005.
- 2005-13 Choose Your Tribe! - Evolution at the Next Level in a Peer-to-Peer network, Hales, D., May 2005.
- 2005-14 Knowledge-Based Jobs and the Boundaries of Firms: Agent-based simulation of Firms Learning and Workforce Skill Set Dynamics, Mollona, E., Hales, D., June 2005.
- 2005-15 Tag-Based Cooperation in Peer-to-Peer Networks with Newscast, Marcozzi, A., Hales, D., Jesi, G., Arteconi, S., Babaoglu, O., June 2005.
- 2005-16 Atomic Commit and Negotiation in Service Oriented Computing, Bocchi, L., Ciancarini, P., Lucchi, R., June 2005.
- 2005-17 Efficient and Robust Fully Distributed Power Method with an Application to Link Analysis, Canright, G., Engo-Monsen, K., Jelasity, M., September 2005.
- 2005-18 On Computing the Topological Entropy of One-sided Cellular Automata, Di Lena, P., September 2005.
- 2005-19 A model for imperfect XML data based on Dempster-Shafer's theory of evidence, Magnani, M., Montesi, D., September 2005.
- 2005-20 Friends for Free: Self-Organizing Artificial Social Networks for Trust and Cooperation, Hales, D., Arteconi, S., November 2005.
- 2005-21 Greedy Cheating Liars and the Fools Who Believe Them, Arteconi, S., Hales, D., December 2005.
- 2006-01 Lambda-Types on the Lambda-Calculus with Abbreviations: a Certified Specification, Guidi, F., January 2006.

On the Quality-Based Evaluation and Selection of Grid Services (Ph.D. Thesis)

Sergio Andreozzi

Technical Report UBLCS-2006-2

March 2006

Abstract

The Grid paradigm enables the coordination and sharing of a large number of geographically-dispersed heterogeneous resources amongst different user communities. It is conceived on the notion of resource abstraction and user abstraction that together define a virtualization layer over the real entities. In this layer, resources can be dynamically grouped into pools and can be accessed by users with the right credentials. Users express their needs over abstract resources and by means of mapping functionalities virtual resources are mapped into physical ones and virtual users are mapped into physical users.

This thesis focuses on resource mapping and explores the related issues of the potentially high number of similar resources and the diversity of the perceived user satisfaction. The investigation shows that users, although having a rich set of terms that can be used to express requirements for the desired resources, lack high-level constructs for representing their needs. Furthermore, an integrated method that starts from the identification and rigorous modelling of attributes and proceeds to the evaluation and selection of the final resources based on the degree of user satisfaction is missing.

In this area, this thesis provides two main contributions. The first is a method for selecting Grid services based on the quality requirements expressed by the user. The method consists of two main phases: (1) the planning phase where the domain of interest is rigorously modelled, the relevant attributes (inherent characteristics) are identified, measurement methods are defined and an analysis method producing quality indicators is proposed; (2) an execution phase where the measures of attributes are performed (objective measures), the user expresses his or her expectations (requirements, subjective measures) and the selection based on the quality indicators takes place (degree of satisfaction).

The second original contribution is a mapping of the proposed method to the concrete level of extensible markup language (XML). In particular, we propose XMatch, a high-level query language that natively supports the constructs for expressing elementary satisfactions as regards attribute values and their relevance as defined in the proposed method. The language is inspired by the XQuery language and enables the analysis of the quality indicator over XML-based representations of Grid resources to be performed, thereby returning those that maximize the satisfaction. A description of a rewriting approach to translate XMatch into XQuery expressions is also provided together with a reference implementation demonstrating its capabilities and functionality.

Acknowledgements

I am very grateful to my supervisor, Professor Danilo Montesi, who guided this work and supported me with his expertise, understanding and many fruitful discussions. I should also like to express my sincere thanks to the head of Research Division at CNAF, Antonia Ghiselli, for her comments and suggestions, and for the freedom I was given to pursue my own research interests.

A special thanks to Tiziana Ferrari who encouraged me to undertake this journey and for her invaluable experience and advice. I am grateful to Rocco Moretti for his contributions and suggestions.

I acknowledge the Italian National Institute for Nuclear Physics for the chance to participate in the DataTAG⁴ and EGEE⁵ research projects that gave me the opportunity to exchange ideas with many people, and work on real problems, whilst having access to a large-scale Grid system.

Finally, I should like to express my deepest gratitude for the constant support and understanding that I have received from my friends and family over the past years.

⁴DataTAG is a project sponsored by the European Union under contract IST-2001-32459

⁵EGEE is a project sponsored by the European Union under contract INFSO-RI-508833

Contents

1	Introduction	5
1	Problem Statement	5
2	Approach	5
3	Organization of the Thesis	6
I	The Grid Paradigm: Principles and Concepts	7
2	Basic Concepts	8
1	User Abstraction	8
2	Resource Abstraction	9
3	Mapping Functionalities	9
4	Summary	10
3	Mapping into a Service Oriented Architecture	11
1	Service Oriented Architecture	11
1.1	<i>Web Services Architecture</i>	11
2	Open Grid Services Architecture	12
2.1	<i>The OGSA Web Services Resource Framework Profile</i>	14
2.2	<i>Other Approaches</i>	15
3	Summary	15
4	Application Scenarios	16
1	Distributed Scientific Collaboration	16
1.1	<i>High-Energy Physics and the Large Hadron Collider</i>	16
2	Healthcare	17
3	Virtual Enterprise	18
4	Summary	18
II	Resource Selection in Grid Systems	19
5	Related Work	20
1	Boolean Selection	20
2	Selection as Constraint-Satisfaction Problem	21
3	Multiple Criteria Decision Analysis	21
4	Semantic-Based Selection	21
5	Preference-Based Selection	22
6	Summary	22
6	Problem Statement	23
1	Commentary	23
2	Summary	24
III	A Method for Quality-Based Service Evaluation	25
7	Representing Grid Services	26
1	Information Modelling	26
2	Representational Theory of Measurement	27
3	Summary	29
UBLCS-2006-2		3

8	A Logical Formalism for Preference Scoring	30
1	Logic Scoring of Preferences 30	
1.1	<i>Elementary Preferences</i> 30	
1.2	<i>Compound Aggregation Functions</i> 31	
2	Summary 33	
9	Service Evaluation Method	34
1	Definition 34	
2	Use Case 37	
2.1	<i>Planning Phase</i> 37	
2.1.1	Conceptual Modelling 37	
2.1.2	Attributes and Measurement Methods 38	
2.2	<i>Execution Phase</i> 40	
2.2.1	User Expected Satisfaction 40	
2.2.2	Satisfaction Evaluation 42	
2.3	<i>Behaviour of the Aggregation Function</i> 43	
3	Summary 43	
IV	A Language for Quality-Based Selection 44	
10	The XMatch Language	45
1	The Main Clause 45	
2	Generation of the Tuple Stream 45	
3	Expressing the Satisfaction 46	
4	Classifying the Satisfactions by Relevance 49	
5	Constructing the Result 51	
6	Use Cases 51	
6.1	<i>Computing, Storage and Network Resources</i> 52	
6.2	<i>Storage Element</i> 53	
7	Summary 55	
11	Rewriting XMatch into XQuery	56
1	Approach 56	
2	A Complete Example 59	
3	Summary 61	
	Conclusion	62
12	XMatch Grammar	63
13	XQuery Functions Module	64

Chapter 1

Introduction

1 Problem Statement

The Grid paradigm enables the coordination and sharing of a large number of geographically-dispersed heterogeneous resources amongst different user communities. It is conceived on the notion of resource abstraction and user abstraction that together define a virtualization layer over the real entities. In this layer, resources can be dynamically grouped into pools and can be accessed by users with the right credentials. Users express their needs over abstract resources and by means of mapping functionalities virtual resources are mapped into physical ones and the virtual users are mapped into physical users.

This thesis focuses on resource mapping and explores the related issues of the potentially high number of similar resources and the diversity of the perceived user satisfaction. The investigation shows that users, although having a rich set of terms that can be used to express requirements for the desired resources, lack high-level constructs for representing their needs. Furthermore, an integrated method that starts from the identification and rigorous modelling of attributes and proceeds to the evaluation and selection of the final resources based on the degree of user satisfaction is missing.

The final goal is to provide users with a language and a tool to express their requirements and preferences and to assess the suitable solutions when submitting a job to a Grid system. Such a tool can be integrated in the Grid scheduling process in order to improve the selection capabilities of current systems.

2 Approach

This work started with the analysis of current approaches used in Grid systems for resource evaluation and selection. It was also investigated how similar problems are solved in other disciplines, especially in the database community. By decomposing the problem in the capability of rigorously representing service characteristics, capability for users to express their expectations flexibly and capability of measuring the degree to which the characteristics fulfill user requirements, we identify the inner concept of quality measurement in this process. In fact, the International Standard Organization (ISO) defines quality as 'degree to which a set of inherent (existing) characteristics fulfils requirements' [Int00].

Starting from this concept, we provide two main contributions. The first is a method for selecting Grid services based on the quality requirements expressed by the user. The method consists of two main phases: (1) the planning phase where the domain of interest is rigorously modelled, the relevant attributes (inherent characteristics) are identified, measurement methods are defined and an analysis method producing quality indicators is proposed; (2) an execution phase where the measures of attributes are performed (objective measures), the user expresses his or her expectations (requirements, subjective measures) and the selection based on the quality indicators takes place (degree of satisfaction).

The second original contribution is a mapping of the proposed method to the concrete level of extensible markup language (XML). In particular, we propose XMatch, a high-level query language that natively supports the constructs for expressing elementary satisfactions as regards attribute values and their relevance as defined in the proposed method. The language is inspired by the XQuery language and enables the analysis of the quality indicator over XML-based representations of Grid resources to be performed, thereby returning those that maximize the satisfaction. A description of a rewriting approach to translate XMatch into XQuery expressions is also provided together with a reference implementation demonstrating its capabilities and functionality.

The overall contribution is very novel and provides an advancements of service selection capabilities in the context of Grid systems. Through this approach, users are able to express their requirements and preferences over the desired resources meaningfully and intuitively and leave to the system the management of the complexity related to the translation of user expectations into the selection process.

3 Organization of the Thesis

In Part I, the concepts and principles that are behind the Grid paradigm are presented. We propose an overview of the Service Oriented Architecture (SOA) since it is the leading approach for engineering Grid systems. Standardization efforts are described together with the relevant interoperability profiles. Application scenarios such as distributed scientific collaboration and virtual enterprise are presented.

In Part II, the relevant approaches to resource selection in Grid systems are reviewed. Similar problems in other disciplines are also investigated and the conclusion is provided by giving the problem statement that this work tackles.

Part III is dedicated to the first contribution of this work, that is, a method for evaluating and selecting Grid services based on the quality requirements expressed by the user. The relevant background on conceptual modelling, representational theory of measurement and Logic Scoring of Preferences (LSP) is first set out. Then, the method as composed by two main phases is described and, to conclude, it is shown how it can be applied in a Grid-related scenario.

In Part IV, the second main contribution of this work is presented, that is the XMatch language. Its constructs are defined and described in detail and two complete use cases are proposed. Furthermore, a description of a rewriting approach to translate XMatch into XQuery expressions is provided.

Part I
The Grid Paradigm: Principles and Concepts

Chapter 2

Basic Concepts

The Grid paradigm evolves the traditional distributed computing approach towards the coordination and sharing of computing, application, data, storage, or network resources across dynamic and geographically dispersed organizations. These resources can be grouped into virtual pools that are accessible by users with the right credentials. Each virtual pool is dynamic and diverse since resources can be added and withdrawn at any time according to their owners discretion.

According to Németh and Sunderam [NS03, NS06], the key properties that make Grid systems different from conventional distributed systems are: (1) resources are abstracted and form virtual pools; (2) users who require access to resources of the virtual pools are different from users who have valid accounts and login rights to physical resources; (3) mapping functions are available for entities translating from virtual to physical resources and users; (4) the number of resources in the pool is in the order of thousands or greater.

In Section 1, we describe the motivations for user abstractions. In Section 2, the need for resources abstraction is presented. Finally, Section 3 is dedicated to the two mapping functionalities.

1 User Abstraction

The dynamic sharing of dispersed resources amongst evolving communities of users from different institutions imposes new challenges to the definition of mechanisms for the management of credentials to be used to authenticate and authorize resource access and usage.

Due to the large number of resources belonging to different administrative domains, it is technically impossible to coordinate and maintain dynamically valid login access (physical user) for the potential users. The approach undertaken that follows the principle of virtualization is that of the definition of new user identities (abstract user) that are dynamically mapped into physical ones during the assignment of a process to a physical resource (see Figure 1).

The concept of user abstraction enables end-users to present themselves using only the Grid-level identity and to be able to access those resources where mapping into physical identities has been defined. In the current Grid systems, the Grid identity is defined in the context of the Grid Security Infrastructure (GSI) [FKTT98, BEF⁺00, WSF⁺03]. This proposal provides mutual authentication, message protection, single sign-on and delegation capabilities. It is based on the Public Key Infrastructure (PKI X.509) [HFPS99] extended with support for proxy certificates [TWE⁺04]. By giving resource providers the capability to enable such a mapping of their managed resources, they also maintain access control.

A further improvement in the management of large communities of abstract users is the extension of the user mapping functionalities so as to accept other types of arguments related to the user [LCB⁺04]. For instance, abstract users can be part of a VO (a Virtual Organization is a new organizational form which manifests itself as a temporary or permanent collection of geographically dispersed individuals, groups, organizational units, either belonging or not belonging to

Figure 1. Abstractions in Grid systems

the same organization, or entire organizations that depend on electronic links in order to complete the production process [Tra97]). Within a certain VO, the user can belong to a certain group or can have a particular role (e.g., [ACd04]). All these attributes related to the abstract user can be considered during the mapping phase to improve the capabilities for a dynamic distribution of resources.

2 Resource Abstraction

An abstract user interacting with a Grid system has very little or no a priori knowledge about the actual type, state and features of the physical resources part of the dynamic pool to which he has access rights. Conversely, he or she has a clear understanding of the resource needs (abstract resource) for the process to be executed (see Figure 1).

By describing the characteristics and preferences of the desired resources for its process, the user can delegate to a Grid system the selection of a suitable physical resource that matches the description of the abstract one. In this way, it is possible to optimize the usage of the available resources amongst a large community of users.

3 Mapping Functionalities

Given the virtual layer where both abstract resources and abstract users live, functionalities are needed to map them into the respective physical resources and physical users for the actual execution of the user process. Such a mapping is performed as an effect of a user request and temporary bindings are created for the life of the user processes.

The user mapping can be based not only on the user abstract identities, but also on other attributes such as the VO membership of the user, the role or group within the VO, or accounting information. By offering trusted mechanisms to manage these attributes, the interested parties can dynamically tune the distribution of resources to abstract users. For instance, VO managers

can add or withdraw a user membership; they can update the user group or role; a site administrator can decide to map a certain group of users of a certain VO to a set of resources with high priority access during daytime.

As regards resource mapping, the related function maps the abstract resource representing the user needs into an appropriate physical one. The mapping performed by the Grid system should be able to deal with both requirements (characteristics that the target resource must have) and preferences (characteristics that the target resource may have). It can also take into account the optimization of the resource distribution.

4 Summary

In this chapter, we have presented the core concepts and principles that are behind the Grid paradigm. We have highlighted how user abstraction and resource abstraction are the basic pillars creating a virtual layer where resources can be dynamically grouped and assigned to users. The resource and user mapping functions provide the necessary binding between these layers. In the following chapter, we will describe how this abstract model is mapped into a service oriented architecture.

Chapter 3

Mapping into a Service Oriented Architecture

In recent years, the Service Oriented Architecture (SOA) [BHM⁺04] has emerged as the standard way of engineering Grid systems [FKNT02]. In this chapter, the details of this architectural style are presented and the main standard specifications that build on top of the Web architecture are summarized (see Section 1). Open Grid Service Architecture (OGSA)[FBA⁺05, FBA⁺06] is then introduced, a standardization effort that defines a set of core capabilities and behavior that address key concerns in Grid systems to enable interoperability (see Section 2).

1 Service Oriented Architecture

A Service Oriented Architecture (SOA) is a form of distributed systems, the main underlying assumption of which is to consider the involved entities as service requesters and service providers exchanging messages through a shared transport mechanism. A service is an abstracted, logical view of actual software components defined in terms of the messages exchanged between provider entity and requester entity, typically carrying out a business-level operation [BHM⁺04].

The message orientation implies that the interaction among services is expressed in terms of the wire format of the messages. This means that any knowledge of the internal structure of an agent (e.g., in-memory data structure) is abstracted and the mapping from the message to the internal of the service is postponed at implementation time. This approach enables platform neutrality of interactive agents (they can be developed using different languages in different operating systems) and deals with the characteristics of the communication over the Internet, where reliability and speed cannot be guaranteed.

1.1 Web Services Architecture

The Web Service Architecture (WSA) [BHM⁺04] is an incarnation of a Service Oriented Architecture in the context of the World Wide Web (WWW). It is defined by the World Wide Web Consortium (W3C) and identifies the global elements of the Web services network that are required in order to ensure interoperability between Web services.

Since the WSA builds on top of the WWW, it inherits its three architectural bases that are (see Figure 1): (1) ‘identification’, agents identify objects in the system, called resources, with Uniform Resource Identifiers (URIs); (2) ‘interaction’, agents communicate using standardized protocols that enable interaction through the exchange of messages which adhere to a defined syntax and semantics; (3) ‘format’, agents represent, describe, and communicate resource state via representations of the resource in a variety of widely-understood data formats [JW04] (agent is a piece of software acting on behalf of a person).

In the WSA, a Web service is defined as ‘a software system designed to support interoperable machine-to-machine interaction over a network. It has an interface described in a machine-

Figure 1. Relationship between identifier, resource and representation

processable format, specifically the Web Services Description Language (WSDL) [CCMW01]. Other systems interact with the Web service in a manner prescribed by its description using SOAP (Simple Object Access Protocol) [Mit03] messages, typically conveyed using HTTP with an XML serialization in conjunction with other Web-related standards' [BHM⁺04]. This definition presents the key features of a SOA, e.g., message orientation and wire format. It also adds a minimal set of constraints as regards technologies to ensure interoperability.

The conceptual stack of interrelated standard protocols for the Web service architecture starts from the downmost layer that consists of the 'messaging mechanism' for communicating document-centric messages. They are based on the Simple Object Access Protocol (SOAP) enabling the exchange of structured and typed information between peers in a decentralized, distributed environment. The 'service description' layer allows to define a set of description documents using the Web Services Description Language (WSDL). The upmost layer is the 'processes layer', concerning process descriptions such as, for instance, the process of discovering service descriptions satisfying specified criteria, the process of describing multi-part and stateful sequences of messages and the aggregation of processes into higher-level processes.

In order to enable interoperability of different implementations of the same set of specifications across platforms, operating systems and programming languages, the Web Services Interoperability (WS-I) organization was set up. WS-I defines normative documents called profiles (e.g., WS-I Basic Profile [BEF⁺04]) that provide implementation guidelines for how related Web services specifications should be used together for best interoperability.

2 Open Grid Services Architecture

The Global Grid Forum (GGF)[GGF] is the community of users, developers, and vendors leading the pervasive adoption of Grid computing in research and industry. The main goals of GGF are

twofold: (1) defining specifications that lead to broadly adopted standards and interoperable software and (2) building an international community for the exchange of ideas, experiences, requirements and best practices.

One of the main outcomes of the activity of GGF is the Open Grid Service Architecture (OGSA)[FBA⁺05, FBA⁺06] defined by the OGSA Working Group. The set of specifications proposes a mapping of the Grid paradigm into Service Oriented Architecture by defining a set of core capabilities and behaviours that address key concerns in Grid systems. OGSA identifies six families of services that together enable a functioning Grid system: Execution Management, Data, Resource Management, Security, Self-Management and Information services.

The Execution Management Services (EMS) are concerned with the problems of instantiating and managing units of work until their completion. These activities require the capability of finding possible candidate resources satisfying the requirements of the unit of works and the capability of selecting the target resources by following certain criteria. Once the resources are identified, they need to be properly configured in order to create a working execution environment for the application (e.g., setting up binary and libraries, staging data). After this, the unit of works can be started and must be managed and monitored until completion. The required capabilities have been grouped into three main sub-categories: (1) resource services that model processing, storage, executables, resource management, and provisioning; (2) job management and monitoring services; (3) resource selection services that collectively decide where to execute a unit of work. In particular, the latter is decomposed in the Candidate Set Generator (CSG), the Execution Planning Services (EPS) and the Reservation services that can perform advance reservation of a resource in order to provide a guaranteed service within a certain time interval.

The Data Services are concerned with the movement and management of a number of different data resources, such as flat files, data streams and databases. They also consider derivations, which are data resulting from asynchronous queries or transformations on other data. The types of activities that must be supported by the data services include remote access, staging, replication, federation, derivation and metadata generation and management. In addition, data services should deal with access transparency, that is they should provide abstract views on the data sources that hide the differences in protocols, interfaces, media, location and data structure.

The Resource Management Services perform several forms of management activities and are categorized by the level of abstraction where they apply. The downmost level is called resource and management refers to the physical and logical resources themselves. Resources are managed directly through their native manageability interfaces and the typical activities involve monitoring (e.g., obtaining the state of the resource), setup and control (e.g., setting up a certain state, rebooting the device) and discovery. These activities also rely on a description given by an information model, which defines their properties, operations, events, and their relationships with each other. The middle level is called infrastructure and provides the base management behaviour of resources. At this level, the different approaches to resource management are abstracted and rely on standard mechanisms. The differences in the information model are able to be integrated in a common solution. The uppermost level is called OGSA functions and refers to the management of typical distributed resource management activities.

The Security Services are concerned with the enforcement of the security-related policy within a (virtual) organization. Security policies are statements about entities involved in a Grid system, interaction mechanisms and contexts, and specify restrictions on the associated attribute values, properties and their relationships. The policy statements (or rules) will be able to be expressed in terms of these entities (e.g., identities, user attributes), resources (i.e., endpoints), and environment characteristics (e.g., time, location, purpose, or the trust level of the requester or request path). These policies can be about various aspects including authorization, authentication, trust, identity mapping, delegation and assurance levels. The functional capabilities and corresponding security services are: authentication, that is the verification of the proof for an asserted identity; identity mapping, that is the capability of transforming an identity living in one identity domain into an identity within another identity domain (policy-driven mapping); authorization, that is resolving a policy-based access-control decision; audit and secure logging, which are responsible for producing records that track security-relevant events; privacy, which is primarily

concerned with the policy-driven classification of personally identifiable information (PII).

The Self-management services are concerned with the automation of the tasks of configuration, healing and optimization needed to keep the Grid operating correctly and meeting the Service Level Agreements (SLAs). They operate by monitoring load and utilization of resources and the running state of the other services. Based on the monitoring data, the management services must make an analysis in order to make sure that all the SLAs can be satisfied. If not, the management services must adjust priorities or provision additional resources. Information services provide the mechanisms for the other Grid services to learn about dynamic events used for status monitoring and directory information used to discover services and logged data.

The Information Services deal with the ability to access and manipulate information about applications, resources and services in the Grid environment efficiently. Different types of information, expected communication pattern or quality of service requirements imply different requirements for these services. Nevertheless, there are recurring structures that justify this category. Information is made available for consumption, either by the originating producer, or through an intermediary (e.g., logging service, notification broker) acting on behalf of the originating producer. Either one or more consumers wish to obtain information from one or more producers, or one or more producers wish to send information to one or more consumers. Producers and consumers should be decoupled and not be required to have any prior knowledge of each other. Consumers may contact a producer (or intermediary) and pull information in one call or they may use a subscription mechanism to receive information as it becomes available. The following capabilities are required: naming, discovery, message delivery, logging and monitoring.

The OGSA-WG produces different types of documents. Amongst them, we should consider two normative documents: specifications describing the precise technical requirements, typically including interfaces, protocols and behaviours, for a conforming hardware or software component; profiles referencing a set of technical specifications and prescribing the ways in which those specifications should be implemented and used in order to perform various classes of operation in an interoperable fashion. In the following sections, the main approaches for the implementation of the OGSA are presented, although a complete implementation of the whole OGSA is still lacking.

2.1 The OGSA Web Services Resource Framework Profile

In this section, we present the OGSA WSRF profile, a normative document addressing issues relating to distributed resource management and Grid computing. This document grounds on the WS-I 1.1 [BEF⁺04] and mandates the use of a set of specifications dealing with the addressing, modelling and management of resource states. In particular, it proposes the adoption of the WS-Addressing [GH05], WS-ResourceProperties [GT06], WS-ResourceLifetime [SB06], WS-BaseNotification [GHM05] and WS-BaseFaults [LM06].

The selected approach for the modelling and management of a resource state in the context of Web services was first introduced by a white paper [CFF⁺04] and a set of specifications currently managed by the WSRF Technical Committee (WSRF-TC) [WSR] and by the WSN Technical Committee (WSN-TC) [WSN] part of the Organization for the Advancement of Structured Information Standards (OASIS)[OAS]. This approach introduces the concept of a stateful resource as a different entity than the Web Service. The stateful resource is described in terms of a set of properties contained in a document and has an identifier that can be used by a Web service for accessing and managing the resource itself. The Web service and the resource pair are called WS-Resource and mechanisms exist to manage its lifecycle, i.e., creation, identity and destruction.

The WS-BaseFaults specification proposes a common mechanism for reporting faults returned by operations on Web services, whilst the WS-BaseNotification describes the basic roles, concepts, and patterns required to allow a subscriber to register interest in receiving notification messages from a notification producer (e.g., a change of a resource property).

The Globus Toolkit 4 [GLO] is a leading implementation of components for building a WSRF-based Grid system.

2.2 Other Approaches

In the previous section, we have seen the characteristics of the Web Services Resource Framework (WSRF), a set of specifications grown up in the context of the OGSA and being standardized by OASIS, the aim of which is to provide the missing functionalities of the WSA for the implementation of the Grid architecture as defined by the GGF.

Other approaches to the implementation of a working Grid system in terms of a SOA exist. They were proposed for two main reasons: immaturity of the WSRF specifications for projects that were supposed to deliver working solutions in the short term [ADD⁺04] and the perceived high level of complexity of WSRF [HWK⁺05]. In this section, we discuss them along with the reasons asserted by them.

During 2004, the Open Middleware Infrastructure Institute (OMII) [OMI] proposed an evolutionary approach to the adoption of Web services related specifications for the implementation of Grid systems. Such an approach is evolutionary in the sense that only widely adopted and mature specifications are considered and the convergence to emerging standards is postponed until they become stable. The proposal, depicted in [ADD⁺04], starts from the WS-I 1.1 profile [BEF⁺04] and extends it considering the following aspects: programming model of Grids for which the Business Process Execution Language (BPEL) [BPE] is suggested; reliable delivery of messages for which WS-ReliableMessaging (WS-RM) [BBC⁺05b] is selected; addressing by means of the WS-Addressing [GH05].

In [HWK⁺05], an alternative solution based on WS-Transfer [ABC⁺04] and WS-Eventing [BCC⁺04] was proposed. WS-Transfer is an approach to the management of the state of resources that follows the Representational State Transfer (REST) architectural style [Fie00]. In fact, it proposes a uniform set of operations for working on resources, i.e., 'Create, Retrieve, Update, Delete' over XML-based representation of resources. WS-Eventing describes a protocol that allows Web services to subscribe to or accept subscriptions for event notification messages. By means of this protocol, a Web service (subscriber) can register interest (subscription) with another Web service (event source) in receiving messages about events (notifications or event messages). A default asynchronous delivery mechanism is provided, but the specification itself is not constrained as regards the possibility of having different approaches.

3 Summary

In this chapter, we have presented Service Oriented Architecture as the leading architectural style for building the current generation of Grid systems. The mainstream is to rely on and extend the Web Service Architecture, an incarnation of a SOA on the foundations of the WWW. Extensions have been proposed to deal with the requirements of a Grid system and the important role of the Global Grid Forum has been depicted. In the next chapter, three important application scenarios that could benefit from the adoption of a Grid will be described.

Chapter 4

Application Scenarios

There are many scenarios where Grid systems may be successfully utilized (e.g., collaborative scientific research, financial risk analysis, product design). In this chapter, we describe three of the main. In Section 1, we describe how a Grid system can help in distributed scientific collaboration with particular focus on High-Energy Physics (HEP), in Section 2, we focus on healthcare, finally, in Section 3 we depict how a Grid can support the Virtual Enterprise view.

1 Distributed Scientific Collaboration

Distributed scientific collaborations are characterized by large-scale projects involving many collaborators from multiple institutions. The success of their interaction and activity depends critically on an infrastructure that connects and integrates widely distributed computing, storage and data resources. In this context, the Grid paradigm plays a key role by reducing barriers to the use of remote resources and by enabling dynamic sharing and coordination of resources for advanced scientific applications and problem solving frameworks.

Another important consideration is that the need for computing power of certain communities (e.g., High-Energy Physics) grows up faster than the computing power per unit cost. This means that the periodical upgrade of the systems owned is not able to satisfy their needs. As regards this aspect, the Grid paradigm offers a way to increase the available resources dynamically by seamlessly integrating external resource providers. Furthermore, it enables the usage of resources available within each community to be optimized by distributing the workload in order to avoid underutilization of available resources.

In summary, a Grid system can provide large scientific collaborations with an abstraction layer to the dispersed resources enabling access to adequate computing capacity available on demand and adequate data capacity with transparent access to sparse replicas. By means of a Grid system, scientists may be able to focus on their application domain problem without the need for considering the issues related to the integration of the distributed resources.

1.1 High-Energy Physics and the Large Hadron Collider

The European Organization for Nuclear Research (CERN) [CER] was founded in 1954 on the border between France and Switzerland, near Geneva. CERN is supported by twenty European countries and its primary objective is to provide the scientific community with facilities to study sub-nuclear particles and forces of matter. The experiments conducted at CERN attract more than 5000 scientists from over 80 countries and 500 universities, for which reason it can be considered as the world leading research laboratory in particle physics.

Currently, CERN is building the Large Hadron Collider (LHC), a machine that consists of a ring of superconducting magnets, 27-km in circumference lying on average 100 m below ground. This machine will enable the constraint of two beams of protons in the twin-aperture magnets and their acceleration in opposite directions. There are four points around the ring where the two

beams can be brought into head-on collision. In each of these four intersections, there is a detector associated to a physics experiment: ATLAS (A Toroidal LHC Apparatus) [ATL], CMS (Compact Muon Solenoid) [CMS], ALICE (A Large Ion Collider Experiment) [ALI] and LHC-B (LHC - Beauty) [LHC]. A detector is a complex structure made of several components that measure and collect information such as particle trajectories and timing. The measuring components produce electronic signals, which are collected by very fast computing elements in real-time with the collision. Only minimal data processing is performed in this phase (on-line). Data are stored on long term devices for off-line analysis.

ATLAS and CMS are general-purpose detectors and will help in the search for Higgs bosons and supersymmetric particles. The ALICE detector will be used to study the plasma produced by colliding lead ions at speeds which will produce energy densities as high as in the first fraction of a second of the beginning of the Universe. The LHC-B detector is designed to study the violation of symmetries and other rare phenomena in B-meson decay. This should lead to an understanding of why there is apparently so little antimatter in the universe, when matter and antimatter should have been produced in equal amounts at the Big Bang.

In each detector, the two opposite beams will generate 40 million collisions per second. After filtering, 100 collisions of interest per second will be required storing and considering that each collision can be represented in a megabyte of data, the required recording rate is 100 MB/s. It is estimated that the four experiments will require to store 10^{10} collisions to be stored each year, that is 10 petabytes/year of data. These data need to be shared amongst physicists all around the world and a processing power in the order of 100K in today's processors will be required.

From the scenario described above, we can extract important requirements for the computing infrastructure needed by the next-generation collider (LHC). Firstly, virtual collaboration, a huge number of scientists belonging to different institutes work on the same topic and need to share the results of the experiments performed by means of the LHC. Secondly, the number of processors needed to analyze the data is at least two orders of magnitude greater than the biggest centralized High-Energy Physics (HEP) computing facility and one order of magnitude greater than today's largest computing centre [TOP]; conversely each scientist has local computing facilities that, considered together could satisfy the community needs.

In the middle of the 1990s, the rapid improvements in communications technologies led academic researchers to begin thinking of making computing power as easy to access as a metaphoric electric power Grid [FKT01]. Ten years later, the Grid paradigm has emerged as a means of enabling the integration, virtualization and management of services and resources in a distributed, heterogeneous environment [KT05].

The High-Energy Physics community was quick to adopt this paradigm and today CERN is able to use the LHC Computing Grid (LCG) [LCG], a distributed data and computing infrastructure spanning around 200 sites, offering 20K processors and 5 PB of data storage. The number of available resources will grow in the coming years as more sites will join the LCG to share their resources. There are several benefits of this approach, amongst which let us mention: (1) a significant reduction of costs for maintaining and upgrading the necessary resources since ownership is spanned across several institutes responsible for them; (2) improved reliability due to the distributed nature of the infrastructure.

2 Healthcare

The term eHealth describes the use of Information and Communication Technologies (ICT) to develop an intelligent and connected environment that enables ubiquitous management of citizens' healthcare, assists health professionals in coping with major collaborative challenges or integrates the advances in health knowledge into clinical practice [DS04].

The challenges to be faced in this context are various. For instance, patient records need to be interconnected and understood across institutions and even national borders. All the information should be secured, especially that concerning personal data, i.e., any piece of information through which the patient may be identified, either directly or in combination with information that is, or

may be, available. Access to the information must be restricted to authorized and authenticated persons. Finally, data must be encrypted to guarantee their confidentiality and integrity, and the electronic archiving of personal data must comply with both European and national laws.

Another important aspect is the capability of discovering trustworthy sources of information for comparison. In certain areas of healthcare, it is necessary to handle huge and dispersed volumes of data, especially in the case of genetic medicine. Another typical requirement of applications in this context is the always-on nature, that is, they must work around the clock. Finally, the need for dealing with heterogeneous medical information due to the lack of widely accepted standards.

In this context, the Grid paradigm is to be considered a vital approach for facing these challenges and working towards the creation of HealthGrids. HealthGrids are Grid infrastructures comprising applications, services or middleware components that deal with the specific problems arising in the processing of biomedical data. They are being designed and developed to deal with data ownership and security requirements, to enable the development of distributed databases and data mining capabilities, to support 'always on' medical applications by offering robustness and fault tolerance, and to empower the creation and adoption of medical information standards.

3 Virtual Enterprise

In recent years, the manufacturing environment has been progressively characterized by dramatic and often unanticipated change. This has led to research in innovative strategies to improve market competitiveness. In this context, one of the most interesting strategies being explored is the concept of the Virtual Enterprise (VE). A virtual enterprise is 'a temporary consortium of autonomous, diverse and possibly geographically dispersed organizations that pool their resources to meet short-term objectives and exploit fast-changing market trends' [DKP⁺99]. Partners involved in a virtual enterprise remain independent and possibly competitive in all activities other than those related to the product. This implies that not all information can be shared.

The lifetime of a virtual enterprise is at most the lifetime of the product or service which constitutes the objective of the collaboration; nevertheless, during its life, partners may join or leave. The success of a virtual enterprise is closely related to the capability of coordinating many tasks and facilitating the sharing of data amongst heterogeneous information systems without compromising the proprietary information assets of any individual organization. Furthermore, a virtual enterprise must be able to reconfigure dynamically in order to maintain the competitiveness in a fast-changing market.

From this short description we can already identify how the virtual enterprise can benefit from the key properties of the Grid paradigm. In fact, the Grid paradigm enables the sharing of part of the different organizations' resources and provides abstractions to build and reconfigure dynamically the resources at a virtual level. These are important characteristics for the minimization of start-up costs and for dealing with the need for flexibility.

4 Summary

In this chapter, we have analyzed three important scenarios where Grid systems can be successfully adopted. The first refers to the distributed scientific collaboration, where to solve the faced problems, the sharing and integration of distributed computing and storage is required. The second refers to the need for ubiquitous management of citizens' healthcare and integration of the advances in health knowledge into clinical practice. The third refers to the Virtual Enterprise, where there is a need for organization agility enabling more efficient business processes and greater responsiveness to change.

Part II
Resource Selection in Grid Systems

Chapter 5

Related Work

In this chapter, the relevant approaches to resource selection in Grid systems are summarized. Proposals in other disciplines that are of interest for the topic considered in this work are also presented. They are categorized by their supporting theory in order to ease the comparison. In particular, Section 1 presents solutions relying on compound boolean predicates with a ranking option for the first work. Section 2 describes a proposal that models the resource selection as a constraint-satisfaction problem. Section 3 presents a work parallel to this in the area of Multiple Criteria Decision Analysis (MCDA) applied to Grid computing. Section 4 deals with the difference in semantics of the resource description and proposes the works that borrow from the Semantic Web community. Finally, Section 5 depicts two works that add the concept of preference to query languages for databases.

1 Boolean Selection

A widely used approach for resource selection in Grid systems relies on the Classified Advertisement (ClassAd) language [Sol03]. It was designed in the context of the Condor distributed computing system [LLM88] where it is used for discovery and allocation of resources. Its use consists of the following phases: (1) providers of computing resources submit advertisements describing their capabilities and declaring constraints and preferences for jobs that they are willing to run; (2) consumers submit advertisements describing their jobs and the desired execution environment in terms of constraints and preferences; (3) a matchmaker process matches the resource and consumer request advertisements. Both resource and request advertisements can express requirements and ranking expressions concerning the counterpart. Requirements are boolean expressions involving constants or ClassAd attributes of the counterpart under evaluation. The rank consists in defining an arithmetic expression synthesizing values used for sorting the services satisfying the constraints.

The bilateral matching approach was later extended with a mechanism called gang-matching [LLM03] to support multilateral matching. It allows the description of the relations holding amongst several participants in the matchmaking process. This is obtained by adding the `Ports` attribute in the ClassAd. This attribute defines the number and characteristics of matching advertisements required for satisfying the ClassAd. In each port, a `Label` that names the candidate is defined. It can be used to refer attributes of a candidate in the context of subsequent ports, thereby conveying information from one match locality to another.

In [SRAAW03, AARW⁺02], a framework to support quality of service (QoS) management in service-oriented Grids is proposed. It includes support for resource and service discovery based on QoS properties. The approach is to model these properties in the WSDL (Web Service Description Language) document describing a service, then to use an extended UDDI (Universal Description and Discovery Integration) to enable QoS-based discovery and selection. The expression of the desired service is based on the boolean logic, therefore this framework enables

the partition of services in two categories: those that satisfy user expectations and those that do not satisfy user expectations.

2 Selection as Constraint-Satisfaction Problem

In [LF04], Liu and Foster propose Redline, a language and matchmaking process that reinterprets the selection of resources as a constraint-satisfaction problem. Their proposal extends the ClassAd approach by enabling to express resources to be expressed with adaptable and negotiable properties and deals with resource selection operations that involve multiple resources or requests. In particular, they identify four types of matchmaking: (1) bilateral matching, that is given a request and a resource, check if they match each other; (2) gang-matching, that is given a request for multiple resources that describes the required properties for every resource and their relationship, and a set of resources, check if these resources satisfy the request; (3) congruence matching, that is given a set of requests and a resource, a match succeeds if there is a congruence amongst these requests and this congruence matches the resource; (4) set matching, that is given a request for a set of resources with particular aggregated properties and a set of resources, a match succeeds if this resource set has the required aggregated properties [LF04]. The Redline language is claimed to support all four types of matching.

3 Multiple Criteria Decision Analysis

Multiple Criteria Decision Analysis is an activity which helps decision-making mainly in terms of choosing, ranking or sorting actions [FGE05]. In this area, Kurowski et al. presented an analysis of the application of MCDA approaches, mainly in the form of decision rules and utility functions, to the problem of Grid resource management [KNOW03]. The main objective of the analysis is the identification of problems, possible techniques, and research directions for the Grid resource management processes from the multiple criteria decision-making perspective.

4 Semantic-Based Selection

Within the Grid community, a group of people have embraced the Semantic Web [SEW] to work on an extension of the current Grid vision called Semantic Grid in which information and services are given well-defined meaning, better enabling computers and people to work in cooperation [SEG]. As regards the problem of service selection, there are several proposals in this area.

The first proposal to be mentioned is an ontology-based matchmaker [TDK03] enabling a flexible and extensible approach for performing Grid resource selection. It allows the definition of ontologies describing resources and user requests. The ontology-based matchmaker performs a semantic-based selection relying on the defined ontologies and offers a ranking phase using the attribute specified in the `RankBy` element.

Another proposal in the context of the Semantic Grid is a matchmaking framework based on three selection stages which are context, semantic and registry selection [LR05]. It proposes a three step discovery process consisting of (1) application context selection where the request is matched within the appropriate application context, (2) semantic selection, where the request is matched semantically and (3) registry selection, where a lookup is performed. This approach allows the separate capture of application and Grid services semantics and supports application developers and Grid services developers in registering application and services semantics separately. For the discovery process, this separation allows a classification of the application semantics in order to find service descriptions in the Grid services ontology. The proposal relies on ontologies defined by means of DAML+OIL [VHPSH01] format (superseded by the Ontology Web Language or OWL) and matching results are ranked by using a semantic similarity matching algorithm.

The last work to be considered is Feta, an architecture for user-oriented semantic service discovery proposed within the bioinformatics domain [LAWG05]. The specific requirements of the application domain led the authors towards a semi-automatic semantic discovery tool where the user makes the final decision on the small set of services resulting from the initial automatic selection. The experience showed that a full automatic semantic selection was too complex and sometimes relied on unrealistic assumptions. For instance, it was recognized that a comprehensive description (i.e., a profile for discovery, a process model for orchestration and a grounding for binding and invocation) using the OWL-based Web Service (OWL-S) [MBL⁺04] was difficult to achieve. Furthermore, even though such formal semantics were available, the discovery of a service supported, for instance, by description logic (DL) reasoning was found to be computationally expensive and with no particular benefits for users searching for services. The final decision was to adopt a light-weight semantics, using the Resource Description Framework (RDF) [Bec04] schema for the classification and entailment; moreover, the RDF Query Language (RDQL) [Sea04] was used for the service selection.

5 Preference-Based Selection

Within the database community, there is a significant literature of works that aims at extending boolean logic-based queries with a preference concept. Let us describe the two most relevant and recent solutions. Kießling proposed a formal language for formulating preference queries based on the Best-Matches-Only (BMO) query model [Kie02, HK05]. It developed a set of constructors and combinators that can be used to write preference expressions. An algebra modelling such operators was defined and extensions for both SQL (Preference SQL [KK02]) and XPATH (Preference XPATH [KHFH01]) were proposed.

Chomicki proposed a logical framework for formulating preferences as strict partial orders by using arbitrary logical formulas [Cho03]. In order to embed such formulas into relation algebra, a single winnow operator that can be parameterized by a preference formula was defined. This enables the rewriting of preference formulas as SQL queries.

6 Summary

In this chapter, we have summarized the relevant approaches to resource selection in Grid systems. We have also integrated the review with approaches to the selection based on both hard and soft constraints in other areas, such as the database community. In the next chapter, the problem statement faced in this work together with the motivations and reference to the given review will be presented.

Chapter 6

Problem Statement

Assigning users requests to actual Grid resources can be modelled as a decision making problem where the mapping functionality has to consider the user expectations in order to make the selection. A user request can involve several types of requirements: (1) a user can require the execution of a single job or the coordinated execution of a set of jobs, typically modelled as a workflow; (2) the user can specify requirements for one or more resources that should serve the request; (3) the user can specify requirements on the network connectivity of the resource executing the job and the input data that can be present in different replicas at several locations; (4) the user may express policies about the job, or the user job itself can be subject to policies provided by the resource provider or by the virtual organization to which the user belongs.

The focus of this work is on users requesting the execution of an individual job. The job may require different types of resources, nevertheless these requirements should be assessable at submission time. This problem is decomposed into three main capabilities that the decision making process should have: (1) the relevant service characteristics that are interesting for the user should be rigorously represented in order to allow meaningful analysis and request, (2) users should be able to express their expectations flexibly as requirements and preferences and (3) an evaluation method for measuring the degree to which the characteristics fulfill the user expectations should exist. Furthermore, a solution able to cope with the XML data model is privileged as this represents a uniform representation layer for the incarnation of the Grid paradigm in terms of a service oriented architecture.

The final goal is to provide users with a language and a tool to express their requirements and preferences and to assess the suitable solutions when submitting a job to a Grid system. Such a tool can be integrated in the Grid scheduling process in order to improve the selection capabilities of current systems.

1 Commentary

As regards the stated problem and the work presented in Chapter 5, the following considerations are provided. In the boolean selection category (see Section 1), the ClassAd language [Sol03] enables the selection of multiple resources and separates the evaluation of hard constraints (expressed by a compound boolean predicate) from soft. The latter can be encoded in a user-defined arithmetic expression that is used to rank the resources. The ranking is in the form of a user-defined arithmetic expression and is considered a difficult mechanism to manage for the final user. This is evident when considering multiple attributes to be aggregated with different unit of measurement and with possibly different levels of importance. The second work mentioned in the same category [SRAAW03, AARW⁺02] has its main advantage in integrating Web services-related technologies with the issue of selecting services, nevertheless it offers only the capability of choosing a single service by means of a compound boolean predicate. This work mentions the notion of quality, nevertheless this is defined in terms of a certain category of attributes.

In the approach of modelling the service selection process as a constraint-satisfaction problem (see Section 2), the work proposed in [LF04] offers a number of extensions to the ClassAd language by enabling different kinds of selection and returning the state of attributes after a matchmaking phase. If not all the defined constraints are matched, a list of non-matching one is returned. However, the proposed solution does not offer the capability of expressing the relevance concept for the constraints.

The analysis presented in Section 3 refers to a parallel work to this one where a subset of MCDA approaches are investigated in the context of Grid resource management. The work does not present a solution and it has a wider set of objectives than those considered here. Whilst we mainly focus on the resource selection at request time, Kurowski et al. consider issues such as adapting applications to a changing environment, imprecise information concerning a state of jobs and resources, and the use of prediction techniques.

In the semantic-based selection category (see Section 4), the three proposals are mainly targeted at dealing with semantic differences in the service description by taking advantage of a background knowledge, but do not offer particular support to users for expressing different relevance of attributes as regards the expectations on their values.

In the preference-based selection category (see Section 5), the two works [Kie02, Cho03] were both proposed within the database community. They both offer support for requirement and preference expressions, they opt nevertheless for a qualitative evaluation and map their model as extensions to the Structured Query Language (SQL).

The problem identified in this work may still be considered an open research area and there are different approaches that have been proposed in recent years and that are also parallel to this work. It should be considered important to tackle the problem from the quality viewpoint. In fact, by analyzing the problem statement, a clear mapping of the required capabilities of the decision process to the definition of quality given by the International Standard Organization (ISO) can be identified: 'degree to which a set of inherent (existing) characteristics fulfils requirements' [Int00, AMM03]. None of the proposed approaches consider in a rigorous manner the quality viewpoint and do not provide a measure of such a degree of fulfillment.

2 Summary

In this chapter, the core problem faced by this work has been presented. The chapter started by describing stated goals and scope, then a commentary on the motivation for this work was given. In the next chapter, the first contribution of this work is presented, that is a method for selecting Grid services based on the notion of quality as regards the requirements expressed by the user.

Part III
A Method for Quality-Based Service Evaluation

Chapter 7

Representing Grid Services

Resources available in Grid systems must be described in a precise and systematic manner if they are to be able to be discovered for subsequent management or use. Such a description is useful in many aspects: for instance it can be the basis for designing a data model for a Grid information service or it can be used to extract the set of terms to be given to end users for the description of the resources they are searching for. The information modelling theory helps in this process as it is concerned with the construction of computer-based symbol structures which capture the meaning of information and organize it in ways that make it understandable and useful to people [My198]. The attributes that are identified in the modelling process can be used in a variety of contexts: for instance, they can be used for resource selection, resource monitoring or for generating reports on the functionality of the whole system. For these reasons, we propose to couple the information modelling theory with the measurement theory [MCJ⁺01]. The latter, in particular, provides a formal mechanism for linking defined information needs to attributes of the real world that can be measured, and lead to a clear understanding of the statistical operations supported by a certain attribute.

In Section 1, we give an overview of the information modelling theory and we set out the current approaches in place within the communities of Grid computing and distributed systems. In Section 2, we present the relevant concepts of the measurement theory.

1 Information Modelling

The main purpose of information modelling is to provide an abstract description of the real world defined in terms of constructs that can be represented in computer systems (e.g., objects, properties, behaviour and relationships) capturing a certain degree of detail depending on the modelling needs of its designers.

Throughout their evolution, information models have been classified into three main categories: physical models, logical models and conceptual models. They represent the historical advance on information modelling from machine-oriented representations towards human-oriented models which are more expressive and can cope with more complex application modelling tasks [My198].

In the context of Grid systems, modelling of resource characteristics is available in several context. The Global Grid Forum proposed an extension of the Common Information Model (CIM) [For03] for modelling characteristics of computational resources useful to users [SF04]. A parallel approach, the GLUE (Grid Laboratory Uniform Environment) Schema [ABF⁺05] proposed a more tailored solution to the need of specific Grid-related projects by modelling computing, storage and network resources. Finally, let us mention the JSDL (Job Submission Description Language) [ABD⁺05], a recent proposal within the GGF defining a language for describing the requirements related to computational jobs to be executed by a Grid.

Conceptual information models can be used to derive logical information models that are

used by the information service (see Section 2) to publish, and therefore enabling discovery, of available resource characteristics and states. As regards this aspect, we observe three main logical models in place in current Grid systems: XML data model for the Globus Monitoring and Discovery Service 4 (MDS4) [MDS05], relational data model for the Relational Grid Monitoring Architecture (R-GMA) [CGN⁺04] and LDAP data model (Lightweight Directory Access Protocol) [WHK97] for the Globus MDS 2 (MDS2) [CFFK01].

2 Representational Theory of Measurement

Measurement is an essential process for many systems as it improves the understanding of them, it enables the prediction of what is likely to happen and work towards a global improvement. In this section, we present an overview of the representational theory of measurement. This theory helps in formalizing our intuition of the real world by ruling the rigorous representation of properties of interest and enabling meaningful analyses and forecasts. We start by considering the following definition [FS98]:

Definition 1 (Measurement) *Measurement is the process by which numbers or symbols are assigned to attributes of entities in the real world in such a way as to describe them according to clearly defined rules.*

An entity is an object or event of the real world, whereas an attribute is a feature or a property of such an object or event. For instance, in a Grid system, an entity can be a computing service and possible properties are the operating system type or the expected response time. When we describe entities by using attributes, we often define attributes by using numbers or symbols. They represent an abstraction of our perception of the real world. In the representational theory of measurement, they are better characterized by the concept of empirical relational system.

Definition 2 (Empirical Relational System) *An empirical relational system is an ordered tuple $\mathcal{ERS} = (\mathcal{EO}, er_1, \dots, er_n, \star_1, \dots, \star_m)$ where \mathcal{EO} is a set of empirical objects, er_i ($i = 1, \dots, n$) are k -ary empirical relationships ($k \geq 2$) defined in \mathcal{EO} , \star_j ($j = 1, \dots, m$) are binary closed operations between empirical objects in \mathcal{EO} .*

An empirical relational system describes the objects of the real world (\mathcal{EO}) and our empirical knowledge of their attributes. For instance, let us consider the entity network service (i.e., a unidirectional communication path from one endpoint to another) and its attribute `Bandwidth`. The set of empirical objects refers to all possible perceptions that we can have of the bandwidth. We may be interested in the ‘is greater than’ empirical relationship, (e.g., the network service NS_1 provides a bandwidth greater than the bandwidth provided by the network service NS_2). As regards operations, we may be interested in evaluating the minimum available bandwidth amongst those provided by a set of network services. This can be achieved by defining the operation \star_1 that selects the minimum bandwidth value amongst the bandwidth values eo_1, \dots, eo_n offered by the network services in the set of interest.

Our empirical knowledge of the entities of interest, that is the empirical relational system, is mapped into a mathematical system in a way that the relations are preserved. Such a system is called formal relational system and is defined as follows:

Definition 3 (Formal Relational System) *A formal relational system is an ordered tuple $\mathcal{FRS} = (\mathcal{FO}, fr_1, \dots, fr_n, \diamond_1, \dots, \diamond_m)$ where \mathcal{FO} is a set of formal objects, fr_i ($i = 1, \dots, n$) are k -ary formal relationships ($k \geq 2$) defined in \mathcal{FO} , \diamond_j ($j = 1, \dots, m$) are binary closed operations between formal objects in \mathcal{FO} .*

A formal relational system represents the mapping to numbers or symbols of the concepts of the real world, in particular, the formal objects relate to the empirical objects, formal relationships model the empirical relationships and formal operations are the mapping of empirical opera-

tions. For instance, considering the entity network service, the empirical objects related to its attribute `Bandwidth` can be mapped into the set of natural numbers \mathbb{N} , the empirical relationship 'is greater than' can be mapped into the formal relationship $>$ and the empirical operation that returns the minimum of a given set of bandwidth can be mapped into the formal relationship $\diamond_1(f_{o_1}, \dots, f_{o_n}) = \min(f_{o_1}, \dots, f_{o_n}) = f_{o_i} | f_{o_i} \leq f_{o_j} \forall j \in [1, n]$.

The link between the empirical relational system and the formal relational system is represented by the concepts of 'measure' and 'measurement scale'.

Definition 4 (Measure μ) Let \mathcal{EO} and \mathcal{FO} be a set of empirical objects and a set of formal objects respectively. A measure $\mu: \mathcal{EO} \rightarrow \mathcal{FO}$ is a function mapping each empirical object $eo \in \mathcal{EO}$ into a formal object $\mu(eo) \in \mathcal{FO}$ (the measurement value).

The measure μ enables the definition of the measurement scale expressing a mapping between the empirical and the formal relational system. Since both relations and operations are preserved, a measurement scale can be considered a homomorphism.

Definition 5 (Measurement Scale) Let $\mathcal{ERS} = (\mathcal{EO}, er_1, \dots, er_n, \star_1, \dots, \star_m)$ and $\mathcal{FRS} = (\mathcal{FO}, fr_1, \dots, fr_n, \diamond_1, \dots, \diamond_m)$ be an empirical relational system and a formal relational system respectively. Let $\mu: \mathcal{EO} \rightarrow \mathcal{FO}$ be a measure. $\mathcal{S} = (\mathcal{ERS}, \mathcal{FRS}, \mu)$ is a measurement scale if and only if $\forall i \in [1, n], \forall j \in [1, m]$ and $\forall eo_1, \dots, eo_k, b, c \in \mathcal{EO}$ ($k \geq 2$) the following properties hold: $er_i(eo_1, \dots, eo_k) \iff fr_i(\mu(eo_1), \dots, \mu(eo_k))$ and $\mu(b \star_j c) = \mu(b) \diamond_j \mu(c)$. If $\mathcal{FO} = \mathbb{R}$ the measurement scale \mathcal{S} is a real measurement scale.

Each empirical object $eo \in \mathcal{EO}$ is associated with a formal object $\mu(eo) \in \mathcal{FO}$ and each empirical relationship er_i is associated with a formal relationship fr_i (see Example 1).

Example 1 Let us consider the attribute operating system type of the entity computing service; a possible set of empirical objects is 'Debian Linux', 'Scientific Linux', 'Microsoft Windows XP'. The respective set of formal objects can be $\{0, 1, 2\}$ and a possible measure is $\mu(\text{Debian Linux}) = 0$, $\mu(\text{Scientific Linux}) = 1$, $\mu(\text{Microsoft Windows XP}) = 2$.

It should be noticed that there are several ways to define a measure and all of them can be valid definitions that preserve the properties of the real world, i.e., of the empirical relational system.

For instance, in the Example 1 we could redefine the measure as $\mu(\text{Debian Linux}) = 2$, $\mu(\text{Scientific Linux}) = 0$, $\mu(\text{Microsoft Windows XP}) = 1$. This would define a different mapping, but it would be still a valid measurement scale. Nevertheless, the more complex the empirical model (in term of numbers of relations and operations), the less alternative measurement scales exist. For instance, let us add the empirical relation 'is preferred than' in our example. A possible mapping of this empirical relationship in a formal one could be ' $<$ ', however, this would imply a different preference in the two proposed measurement scales, hence they are no longer homomorphism for the same empirical perception.

The problem of evaluating whether a mapping from a measurement scale to another is acceptable is better described in terms of the concepts of 'admissible transformation' for a measurement scale and 'meaningful predicate' about a measure.

Definition 6 (Admissible Transformation) Let $\mathcal{S} = (\mathcal{ERS}, \mathcal{FRS}, \mu)$ be a measurement scale ($\mathcal{ERS} = (\mathcal{EO}, er_1, \dots, er_n, \star_1, \dots, \star_m)$, $\mathcal{FRS} = (\mathcal{FO}, fr_1, \dots, fr_n, \diamond_1, \dots, \diamond_m)$, $\mu: \mathcal{EO} \rightarrow \mathcal{FO}$). If $g: \mathcal{FO} \rightarrow \mathcal{FO}$ is a function where $\mathcal{S}' = (\mathcal{ERS}, \mathcal{FRS}, g \circ \mu)$ (\circ is the composition operator between functions) is still a measurement scale, then g is an admissible transformation for the measurement scale \mathcal{S} . $\mathcal{G}_{\mathcal{S}}$ is the set of all admissible transformations for the measurement scale \mathcal{S} .

This definition can be interpreted as saying that if we have a measurement scale for a certain attribute of an entity, we can invent other, equally good scales by applying admissible transfor-

mations to the original scale. The concept of admissible transformation is essential to define the meaningfulness of a predicate concerning the measures of objects.

Definition 7 (Meaningful Predicate) *Let $S = (\mathcal{E}\mathcal{R}\mathcal{S}, \mathcal{F}\mathcal{R}\mathcal{S}, \mu)$ be a measurement scale. A predicate based on the measure μ is meaningful if and only if its truth value is invariant with respect to the set \mathcal{G}_S of all admissible transformations for the measurement scale S .*

On the basis of Definitions 6 and 7, we can identify different types of measurement scales. The major types are reputed to be:

1. **Nominal Scale:** the function g is one to one. The measured objects are partitioned in classes; all admissible transformations must maintain unaltered the classes.
2. **Ordinal Scale:** the function g is strictly increasing. It is a nominal scale with an order relation amongst the classes; all admissible transformations must maintain unaltered the order amongst the classes.
3. **Interval Scale:** $g(x) = ax + b$ ($a, b \in \mathbf{R}$). It is an ordinal scale whose admissible transformations must maintain the difference amongst the values associated to the measured objects.
4. **Ratio Scale:** $g(x) = ax$ ($a \in \mathbf{R}$). It is an interval scale, the admissible transformations of which must maintain constant the ratio of the values associated to the measured objects.
5. **Absolute Scale:** $g(x) = x$. It is a ratio scale, the only admissible transformation of which is the identity function.

Each measurement scale presented above includes the preceding measurement scales. Furthermore, starting from the nominal scale to the absolute scale, there is a progressive decrease of admissible transformations until they consist of the identity function only. Finally, it is important to point out that if measurement scales are not real, then the concepts of 'order', 'difference' and 'ratio' presented above need to be redefined in the context of the set of formal objects presented in the measurement scale.

The identification of a measurement scale type has two fundamental advantages: (1) it enables to understand what all the possible acceptable measurement scales are and (2) to know what the statistics that are supported are (for instance, the ordinal scale supports the median or percentile, whilst it does not support the mean or the standard deviation).

3 Summary

In this chapter, we have stated the importance of a rigorous description of resources part of a Grid system as they need to be discovered in an automatic fashion. We have proposed coupling the information modelling theory to the representational theory of measurement as a way to model, measure and share the information related to the resources needed to perform the discovery and selection. In the next chapter, a method for measurement of the user satisfaction as regards values associated to characteristics and state of available resources is presented. This will be an important pillar that together with what has been presented in this chapter, will be the basis for the definition of the service evaluation model.

Chapter 8

A Logical Formalism for Preference Scoring

In this chapter, the relevant theory concerning the Logic Scoring of Preferences (LSP) [Duj96, SJB⁺87] is presented. It is a method for the quantitative evaluation, comparison and selection of complex systems. LSP grounds on the Continuous Preference Logic (CLP) and supports in decision making problems by providing evaluation features that are close to the observable properties of human reasoning [Duj05].

1 Logic Scoring of Preferences

The Logic Scoring of Preferences (LSP) is a method for the quantitative evaluation, comparison and selection of complex systems [Duj96, SJB⁺87]. In particular, decisions about complex systems rely on three important steps: (1) decomposition of the system into a set of components, (2) specification of component requirements and assessment of the level of satisfaction of requirements, (3) aggregation of the component preferences in an overall score.

In Section 1.1, the elementary criteria of satisfaction that are used to express the satisfaction degree associated to the values returned by a measurement of an attribute are introduced. In Section 1.2, the aggregation functions that enable the aggregation of many satisfactions are presented.

1.1 Elementary Preferences

The elementary criteria of satisfaction consist in defining specific functions associated to the values of measurements concerning the attributes of the entities to be examined. These functions map each possible value into a number $e \in [0, 1]$ (i.e., $e = 0$ means ‘no satisfaction’, whereas $e = 1$ means ‘full satisfaction’) expressing the satisfaction for each possible value. Therefore, the elementary criteria of satisfaction are defined depending on the set of possible measurement values. There are many ways to define these functions, but those that privilege simplicity and clarity are preferred. The three main ways of dealing with these principles are [Duj96]: by enumeration of the possible values, by absolute ranking and by relative ranking.

The criterion ‘by enumeration’ can be exemplified as follows. Let us consider the attribute ‘supported `OSTYPE`’ (a_{os}) of a computing service and let us suppose that its possible values are 0 for ‘RedHat Linux’, 1 for ‘Debian Linux’ and 2 for ‘Microsoft Windows XP’. If the user expectation is to run its job on a RedHat Linux environment, then its elementary criterion of satisfaction can be expressed as follows: $e_{os} = 1$ if the supported `OSTYPE` is 0 (RedHat Linux), $e_{os} = 0$ if the supported `OSTYPE` is 1 (Debian Linux) or 2 (Microsoft Windows XP). It is important to remark that this criterion requires that all possible values returned by a measurement of the attribute under consideration should be able to be listed.

The criterion ‘by absolute ranking’ implies that each value is individually mapped to an elementary satisfaction, but an ordering amongst the values exist. For instance, let us consider the ‘Estimated Response Time’ (a_{ert}) of a computing service. We can order the possible values in such a way that, for values greater than the maximum tolerated response time ert_{max} , a null satisfaction is returned ($e_{ert} = 0$); for values lower than the minimum required response time ert_{min} , a full satisfaction is returned ($e_{ert} = 1$); for values between ert_{min} and ert_{max} , the satisfaction linearly decreases.

The criterion ‘by relative ranking’ implies that the mapping of a single value to an elementary satisfaction requires a comparison with the values that other entities own for the same attribute. For instance, let us consider again the attribute ‘Estimated Response Time’ (a_{ert}) of a computing service. We can order the possible values in such a way that, when the value is the maximum amongst the available services, a null satisfaction is returned ($e_{ert} = 0$), when the value is the minimum amongst the available services, a full satisfaction is returned ($e_{ert} = 1$); for values between $min(a_{ert_i})$ and $max(a_{ert_j})$, the satisfaction linearly decreases.

1.2 Compound Aggregation Functions

In this section, we consider the aggregation of several elementary satisfactions into a global score. The method prescribes the definition of functions returning a global satisfaction $E \in [0, 1]$. Such functions are based on the satisfactions e_1, \dots, e_n defined by n elementary criteria to be aggregated and by their respective weights w_1, \dots, w_n . These weights can be selected in order to reflect the relevance of the attribute that the satisfaction refers to. Besides, they must be positive (i.e., $w_i > 0 \forall i$) and normalized (i.e., $\sum_{i=1}^n w_i = 1$). A wide spectrum of nonlinear multi-criteria scoring functions has been defined in order to model simultaneity (i.e., e_i and e_j have to be simultaneously greater than a threshold), neutrality, replaceability (i.e., a high value of e_i can compensate a low value of e_j) and other input relationships. These scoring functions, defined in [Duj96], have the following generalized form:

$$E = (w_1 e_1^r + \dots + w_n e_n^r)^{\frac{1}{r}} \quad (1)$$

where $-\infty \leq r \leq +\infty$. By varying the value of r , a spectrum of aggregation functions is generated. This spectrum encompasses the most common aggregation functions, including the weighted arithmetic and geometric means. The following theorem [Bul03] helps in understanding how E depends on the r parameter.

Theorem 1 (Weighted Power Mean Inequality) *Let $r_1, r_2 \in \mathbf{R}$ such that $r_1 > r_2$, w_1, \dots, w_n ($w_i > 0 \forall i$ and $\sum_{i=1}^n w_i = 1$), $x_1, \dots, x_n \in \mathbf{R}^+$ then*

$$(w_1 x_1^{r_1} + \dots + w_n x_n^{r_1})^{\frac{1}{r_1}} \geq (w_1 x_1^{r_2} + \dots + w_n x_n^{r_2})^{\frac{1}{r_2}}$$

with equality if and only if $x_1 = x_2 = \dots = x_n$

Proof.

The proof relies on the Jensen inequality [Bul03]: let f be a convex function on an interval I and let w_1, \dots, w_n be nonnegative real numbers ($\sum_{i=1}^n w_i = 1$), then for all $x_1, \dots, x_n \in I$ the following inequality holds:

$$w_1 f(x_1) + \dots + w_n f(x_n) \geq f(w_1 x_1 + \dots + w_n x_n)$$

The proof is structured in 3 cases considering both r_1 and r_2 different than zero (the case of either r_1 or r_2 equal to zero can be deduced from these cases by taking the limit).

Case 1 ($r_1 > r_2 > 0$): the Jensen inequality for the convex function $f(x) = x^{\frac{r_1}{r_2}}$ applied to $x_1^{r_2}, \dots, x_n^{r_2}$ gives $w_1 x_1^{r_1} + \dots + w_n x_n^{r_1} \geq (w_1 x_1^{r_2} + \dots + w_n x_n^{r_2})^{\frac{r_1}{r_2}}$ and taking the $\frac{1}{r_1}$ -th power of both sides yields the desired inequality.

Case 2 ($0 > r_1 > r_2$): the function $f(x) = x^{\frac{r_1}{r_2}}$ is concave, so Jensen inequality is reversed; however taking $\frac{1}{r_1}$ -th power reverses the inequality again.

Case 3 ($r_1 > 0 > r_2$): the function $f(x) = x^{\frac{r_1}{r_2}}$ is convex and taking $\frac{1}{r_1}$ -th power preserves the inequality. \square

Theorem 1 enables to assert that when the r parameter increases and all other parameters are constant, E increases as well. To complete our analysis, we also need Theorem 2. It implies that the provided aggregation function respects the natural intuition of a person, that is the increment of an elementary satisfaction implies the increment of the global satisfaction when all other elementary satisfactions are constant.

Theorem 2 (Monotonicity of the Weighted Power Mean) *Let $f(e_i) = (w_1 e_1^r + \dots + w_i e_i^r + \dots + w_n e_n^r)^{\frac{1}{r}}$ be the weighted power mean where e_i is the independent variable in the interval $I = [0, 1]$ and e_j, w_h and r are constant ($i = 1, \dots, n; j = 1, \dots, n; j \neq i; h = 1, \dots, n$), then $f(e_i)$ is an increasing monotone function.*

Proof.

By proving that $f'(e_i) \geq 0$ for all $e_i \in (0, 1)$, we can assert that $f(e_i)$ is increasing monotone.

Let us define $K = \sum_{j=1, j \neq i}^n w_j x_j^r$, we can write $f(e_i) = (K + w_i e_i^r)^{\frac{1}{r}}$. Then we can compute:

$$f'(e_i) = \frac{1}{r}(K + w_i e_i^r)^{\frac{1-r}{r}}(w_i r e_i^{r-1}) = w_i \frac{e_i^{r-1}}{(K + w_i e_i^r)^{\frac{r-1}{r}}}$$

since the following properties hold:

- $e_i \in (0, 1) \Rightarrow e_i^{r-1} > 0$
- $K \geq 0, w_i \in (0, 1), e_i \in (0, 1) \Rightarrow (K + w_i e_i^r)^{\frac{r-1}{r}} > 0$

we can assert that $f'(e_i) > 0$, hence $f(e_i)$ is strictly increasing monotone in I . \square

In order to capture the desired logical relationship and intensity of polarization of the aggregation function, the r parameter must be selected depending on: (1) the number n of elementary satisfactions to be aggregated and (2) the conjunction degree $c \in [0, 1]$ ($c = 0$ means pure disjunction and $c = 1$ pure conjunction, see Table 1). These relationships are captured by equations 2 and 3.

$$\bar{E}(r, n) = \int_0^1 \dots \int_0^1 \left(\frac{1}{n} e_1^r + \dots + \frac{1}{n} e_n^r \right)^{\frac{1}{r}} de_1 \dots de_n \quad (2)$$

Equation 2 can be considered as the expected aggregate satisfaction of n equally weighted elementary satisfactions where all possible satisfaction combinations are equally likely. $\bar{E}(r, n)$ is inversely proportional to c , that is smaller values for r are obtained with greater values of c .

$$c = \frac{\bar{E}(+\infty, n) - \bar{E}(r, n)}{\bar{E}(+\infty, n) - \bar{E}(-\infty, n)} \quad (3)$$

Equation 3 defines c as a linear interpolation between the minimal and maximal values of $\bar{E}(r, n)$ for a fixed n . Given a certain desired level of conjunction degree c for a certain number n of elementary satisfactions, the value r is computed by solving Equations 2 and 3 numerically [SJB⁺87]. If $r > 1$, equation 1 models the disjunction or replaceability of inputs; if $r < 1$, equation 1 models the conjunction or simultaneity of inputs; if $r = 1$, equation 1 is neutral in the aggregation. Nine basic aggregation functions have been considered in [Duj96] and are reported in Table 1.

A useful notation based on [SJB⁺87] is presented in Figure 1a. An aggregation function is represented by a circle; for each satisfaction e_i a weighted entry arc is defined ($i = 1, \dots, n; \sum_{i=1}^n w_i = 1$); finally, for each circle there is a single exit arc (the synthesized global satisfaction). Moreover, the aggregation functions can be composed in order to produce other functions enabling the definition of aggregation criteria based on a particular logic. For instance, if we need

Table 1. The aggregation functions for the elementary criteria of satisfaction

Name	Symbol	r_2	r_3	r_4	r_5
Disjunction	D	$+\infty$	$+\infty$	$+\infty$	$+\infty$
Strong QD	D ⁺	9.52	11.09	12.28	13.16
Medium QD	DA	3.93	4.45	4.82	5.09
Weak QD	D ⁻	2.02	2.19	2.30	2.38
Arithmetic Mean	A	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00
Weak QC	C ⁻	0.26	0.20	0.17	0.16
Medium QC	CA	-0.72	-0.73	-0.71	-0.67
Strong QC	C ⁺	-3.51	-3.11	-2.18	-2.61
Conjunction	C	$-\infty$	$-\infty$	$-\infty$	$-\infty$

Figure 1. Aggregation functions: notation to represent (a) the aggregation functions and (b) the conjunctive partial absorption function

to aggregate a satisfaction e_p that must cross a fixed threshold so that $E > 0$ and a satisfaction e_s for which we admit $E > 0$ even if $e_s = 0$, then we resort to the ‘conjunctive partial absorption function’ (see Figure 1b). The weighted arithmetic mean function (A) is the input of the average quasi-conjunction function (CA) and the weights are arranged as depicted. A principal satisfaction e_p equal to zero implies $E = 0$, apart from the value of the secondary satisfaction e_s . On the contrary, when e_p is greater than zero, the global satisfaction E is positive. Finally, $e_p = e_s = 1$ implies the largest global satisfaction ($E = 1$).

2 Summary

In this chapter, we have presented the relevant theory concerning the Logic Scoring of Preferences (LSP) method. This theory will be used to define the service evaluation method in the next chapter.

Chapter 9

Service Evaluation Method

In this chapter, a method is proposed for a quality-based evaluation of a set of resource offers as regards user expectations [ACMM04b, ACMM04a, ACMM05a]. In Section 1, the method is described relying on the concepts introduced in the previous chapters, whilst in Section 2, the method is exemplified in the context of Grid systems.

1 Definition

In this section, a method for the evaluation of Grid services is presented. The fundamental assumption consists in considering the evaluation of a service in terms of the satisfaction degree concerning the admissible measurement values of its attributes of interest. There are two main phases to this method: (1) a planning phase where the relevant attributes are identified, a rigorous mapping to a formal system is defined and an evaluation method is proposed; (2) an execution phase where the measures of attributes are performed (objective measures), the user expresses his or her expectations (subjective measures) and the evaluation takes place. In Figure 1, the main components of the proposed method are presented and in the remaining part are explained in more details.

The planning phase is performed by experts who analyze user needs in terms of information that should be available at request time for a service in order to express their interests meaningfully. The first step is the definition of conceptual models for the involved entities. Such models capture the domain where the measurements can be derived and help in understanding how the evaluation behaves when moving back the evaluation result to the real world. Since services are the result of an engineering process, conceptual models may already exist and can be reused and extended if needed. In the method presented here (see Figure 1, step 1), the adoption is proposed of the UML (Unified Modeling Language) [UML05] class diagram for several reasons: UML is one of the most common approaches to conceptual modelling; several existing tools are available; it is already adopted within the Grid community [ABF⁺05], and in general within the distributed systems management area [For03]. On the basis of this model and by means of an analysis of user needs, measurable concepts (attributes) can be inferred (see Figure 1, step 2) and a rigorous modelling targeted at the evaluation process can be applied. This process involves the definition of a measure, a measurement scale and a measurement method for each attribute (see Figure 1, step 3).

Definition 8 (Attribute and Measurement Scale) *Let A be the set of attributes of the entities involved in the evaluation, AM is the set of pairs: (a, S_a) where $a \in A$ and $S_a = (\mathcal{E}RS_a, \mathcal{F}RS_a, \mu_a)$ is a measurement scale.*

The next step within the planning phase is the definition of the evaluation method, that is, a mechanism given to the user so that he or she may express his or her expectations about attribute

Figure 1. Quality-Based Evaluation Method

values of interests. For this task, the use of the Logic Scoring of Preferences using the concepts defined in Section 1 is proposed.

Definition 9 (Elementary Criteria of Satisfaction Set) Let A be the set of attributes of the entities involved in the evaluation, EC_A is the set of elementary criteria of satisfaction for each $a \in A$.

The following equivalence relation is defined in order to identify equivalence relevance classes for the attributes, i.e., to model relevance between attributes.

Definition 10 (Relevance Relation) Let A be the set of attributes of the entities involved in the evaluation, a_i and a_j be elements of A , then \sim_{REL} is an equivalence relation on A defining a collection of pairs (a_i, a_j) where $a_i \sim_{REL} a_j$ means that the satisfaction concerning the values of a_i is as relevant as the satisfaction concerning the values of a_j .

Both Definition 9 and 10 are part of step 4 in Figure 1. As regards the relevance relation, there are no limits to the number of possible classes that can be defined. Nevertheless, the use of three main classes is suggested as they are sufficient for meaningful use cases. The first class is ‘essential’, that is if a non-satisfying value is offered by the service provider, then the global satisfaction will be insufficient and agreement cannot be reached. The second category considered is ‘desired’, that is, if a non-satisfying value is offered by the service provider, then agreement can still be reached, even if the global satisfaction decreases. The third category considered is ‘optional’, that is, non-satisfying values offered by the service provider slightly affect the global satisfaction because the expected service is reputed to be best effort as regards this category. The next definition introduces the functions needed to aggregate the values returned by the elementary criteria of satisfaction (see Figure 1, step 5).

Definition 11 (Aggregation Functions Set) AF_{EC_A} is the set of functions for the aggregation of the values returned by the elementary criteria of satisfaction in EC_A .

Figure 2. General pattern for defining the aggregation functions

The definitions given above compose the Service Evaluation Method (*SEM*) that can be applied to a single service offer. It enables the evaluation of its quality as regards user expectations and can be synthesized by the following function:

$$SEM : (AM, \sim_{REL}, EC_A, AF_{EC_A}) \rightarrow [0, 1] \quad (1)$$

Equation 2 and Figure 2 express how the arguments of the function *SEM* have to be used in order to obtain the overall satisfaction degree.

$$\left. \begin{array}{l}
 \underbrace{(a_1, \mathcal{ERS}_{a_1}) \xrightarrow{\mu_{a_1}} (a_1, \mathcal{FRS}_{a_1}) \xrightarrow{ec_{a_1}} e_{a_1}}_{(a_1, S_{a_1})} \\
 \underbrace{(a_2, \mathcal{ERS}_{a_2}) \xrightarrow{\mu_{a_2}} (a_2, \mathcal{FRS}_{a_2}) \xrightarrow{ec_{a_2}} e_{a_2}}_{(a_2, S_{a_2})} \\
 \vdots \\
 \underbrace{(a_n, \mathcal{ERS}_{a_n}) \xrightarrow{\mu_{a_n}} (a_n, \mathcal{FRS}_{a_n}) \xrightarrow{ec_{a_n}} e_{a_n}}_{(a_n, S_{a_n})}
 \end{array} \right\} \sim_{REL} \left(\begin{array}{l}
 a_2 \rightarrow e_{11} \\
 \dots \\
 a_5 \rightarrow e_{1k_1} \\
 \\
 a_4 \rightarrow e_{21} \\
 \dots \\
 a_9 \rightarrow e_{2k_2} \\
 \vdots \\
 a_6 \rightarrow e_{m-11} \\
 \dots \\
 a_n \rightarrow e_{m-1k_{m-1}} \\
 \\
 a_1 \rightarrow e_{m1} \\
 \dots \\
 a_7 \rightarrow e_{mk_m}
 \end{array} \right) \quad (2)$$

Considering equation 2 and Figure 2: (1) the measurement scales for the attributes under investigation are defined; (2) the satisfaction concerning the value of each attribute is produced by its respective elementary criterion of satisfaction; (3) the satisfactions reputed to be of the same relevance are grouped together by means of \sim_{REL} ; (4) the overall score is obtained by using the pattern in Figure 2 by firstly (4a) aggregating the satisfactions belonging to the same category and secondly (4b) by performing the aggregation of the satisfactions synthesized for each category.

The execution phase envisions the performing of the measurement methods for the attributes in order to generate the values (see Figure 1, step 6). In a real scenario, this activity is typically performed in a periodic fashion and values are collected so that when they need to be consumed, they are already available. When a user needs a resource, (see Figure 1, step 7), he or she has to describe his or her expectations in terms of the concepts in Definitions 9 and in 10. On the basis of the attribute values, the user expectations and the evaluation method, we can perform

the analysis by using the mechanism defined in the planning phase (see Figure 1, step 5) in order to produce the global preference score (see Figure 1, step 8). This indicator provides a measure of the degree to which a certain resource satisfies user expectations. By using this value for each candidate resource and by following the maximization principle of the user satisfaction (decision criteria, see Figure 1, step 9) the final decision can be taken and represents the information product of the evaluation (see Figure 1, step 10).

2 Use Case

The selected use case that exemplifies the current proposal focuses on core Grid services that refer to computing, storage and network resources. In particular, ‘computing service’ is defined as a uniquely identified Grid service that can provide a user software application for computing power in a certain execution environment; ‘storage service’ as a uniquely identified Grid service that manages a storage space; and ‘network service’ as a uniquely identified service that offers unidirectional communication capability between network domains that are meant as sets of services sharing the same connectivity [ACGV04]. The network service is considered as unidirectional because of the nature of the characterizing parameters (i.e., the achievable bandwidth from domain A to domain B can be different from the bandwidth from domain B to domain A).

These services can be dynamically composed on the basis of user requirements to set up and provide complex and on-demand services. As regards the possible scenario for a user request, the possibility is considered of requesting the execution of a single-processor application where the target operating system type and version, the processor family, and the minimization of response time can be specified. Furthermore, the user can express the availability for certain amount of storage space where the output of the computation will be permanently stored. Finally, requirements for bandwidth and round trip time between the location where the computation is performed and the location where the storage space is available can be required.

2.1 Planning Phase

In the planning phase, we start by defining a conceptual model of available resources that capture the details of interest for a service selection.

2.1.1 Conceptual Modelling

In Figure 3, a conceptual model of the reality of interest described by means of a UML class diagram is shown. In this model, a Domain is a concept aggregating a set of Grid services that share similar network connectivity characteristics. It is an abstract concept introduced to aggregate network measurement values on a per-domain basis and is characterized by a unique identifier (URI) (see [ACGV04] for more details about this approach). It aggregates a set of computing and storage services and can have one or more network services either outgoing or ingoing.

The Computing Service (CS) is characterized by a unique identifier (URI), the functional state of the service (State), processor family of the underlying system (ProcessorFamily), the operating system type of the offered execution environment (OSType), the processor family of the underlying system (ProcessorFamily), the number of free slots that can accommodate new running single-processor jobs (FreeJobSlots), the number of total slots that can accommodate single-processor jobs (TotalJobSlots), the number of jobs that are being executed (RunningJobs) and the number of jobs that have been queued and the execution of which is not yet started (WaitingJobs). The computing service owns a relationship with the Domain entity.

A Storage Service (SS) is characterized by a unique identifier (URI), the functional state of the service (State), the available storage space expressed in gigabytes (AvailableSpace), an adimensional value expressing how much data continues to be available at a required level of performance in situations ranging from normal to disastrous (DataAvailability), an adimensional value expressing how much committed data is saved by the system such that, even in the event of a failure and system restart, the data is available in its correct state (Durability). The storage service owns a relationship with the Domain entity.

Figure 3. Conceptual model of the entities in the use case

A Network Service (NS) is characterized by a unique identifier (URI), the functional state of the service (*State*), the amount of network bandwidth for the application expressed in Mb/s (*Bandwidth*), the Round Trip Time (RTT) (*RoundTripTime*) in ms, the service class identifying the service category (*Class*). The network service owns a relationship to the source Domain and another to the destination Domain.

2.1.2 Attributes and Measurement Methods

Starting from the conceptual model defined in the previous section, the selection of the meaningful attributes of the entities under investigation is performed and a measurement method for each of them defined. Considering the computing service entity, the relevant attributes are: (a_1) *OSType*; (a_2) *ProcessorFamily*; (a_3) *WaitingJobs*; (a_4) *RunningJobs*; (a_5) *FreeJobSlots*. As regards the storage service entity, the considered attributes are: (a_6) *Durability*; (a_7) *AvailableSpace*; (a_8) *DataAvailability*. Concerning the network service entity, the following attribute are considered: (a_9) *Bandwidth*, (a_{10}) *RoundTripTime*. Finally, the relevant attributes for both the computing and storage service deriving from the association to the domain concept are: (a_{11}) Membership in the source domain of the Network Service *ns*; (a_{12}) Membership in the destination domain of the Network Service *ns*.

The measurement scales for the attributes of the entities under investigation are defined. The empirical and formal operations are not considered because they are not used in the definition of measures and elementary criteria of satisfaction.

a₁ OSType

- \mathcal{ERS}_{a_1} : (1) \mathcal{EO}_{a_1} is {Scientific Linux, Debian Linux, MS Windows XP};
(2) er_{a_1} = 'is equal to'
- \mathcal{FRS}_{a_1} : (1) \mathcal{FO}_{a_1} = {0, 1, 2}; (2) fr_{a_1} = '='
- The measure $\mu_{a_1}: \mathcal{EO}_{a_1} \rightarrow \mathcal{FO}_{a_1}$ is:

$$\mu_{a_1}(x) = \begin{cases} 0 & \text{if } x = \text{Scientific Linux} \\ 1 & \text{if } x = \text{Debian Linux} \\ 2 & \text{if } x = \text{MS Windows XP} \end{cases}$$

a₂ ProcessorFamily

- \mathcal{ERS}_{a_2} : (1) \mathcal{EO}_{a_2} = {IA32, IA64, PPC32}; (2) er_{a_2} = 'is equal to'
- \mathcal{FRS}_{a_2} : (1) \mathcal{FO}_{a_2} = {0, 1, 2}; (2) fr_{a_2} = '='
- The measure $\mu_{a_2}: \mathcal{EO}_{a_2} \rightarrow \mathcal{FO}_{a_2}$ is:

$$\mu_{a_2}(x) = \begin{cases} 0 & \text{if } x = \text{IA32} \\ 1 & \text{if } x = \text{IA64} \\ 2 & \text{if } x = \text{PPC32} \end{cases}$$

a₃ WaitingJobs

- \mathcal{ERS}_{a_3} : (1) \mathcal{EO}_{a_3} = $\{x \mid x \in \mathbb{N}\}$; (2) er_{a_3} = 'is greater than'
- \mathcal{FRS}_{a_3} : (1) \mathcal{FO}_{a_3} = $\{x \mid x \in \mathbb{N}\}$; (2) fr_{a_3} = '>'
- The measure $\mu_{a_3}: \mathcal{EO}_{a_3} \rightarrow \mathcal{FO}_{a_3}$ is $\mu_{a_3}(x) = x$

a₄ RunningJobs

- \mathcal{ERS}_{a_4} : (1) \mathcal{EO}_{a_4} = $\{x \mid x \in \mathbb{N}\}$; (2) er_{a_4} = 'is greater than'
- \mathcal{FRS}_{a_4} : (1) \mathcal{FO}_{a_4} = $\{x \mid x \in \mathbb{N}\}$; (2) fr_{a_4} = '>'
- The measure $\mu_{a_4}: \mathcal{EO}_{a_4} \rightarrow \mathcal{FO}_{a_4}$ is $\mu_{a_4}(x) = x$

a₅ FreeJobSlots

- \mathcal{ERS}_{a_5} : (1) \mathcal{EO}_{a_5} = $\{x \mid x \in \mathbb{N}\}$; (2) er_{a_5} = 'is greater than'
- \mathcal{FRS}_{a_5} : (1) \mathcal{FO}_{a_5} = $\{x \mid x \in \mathbb{N}\}$; (2) fr_{a_5} = '>'
- The measure $\mu_{a_5}: \mathcal{EO}_{a_5} \rightarrow \mathcal{FO}_{a_5}$ is $\mu_{a_5}(x) = x$

a₆ Durability

- \mathcal{ERS}_{a_6} : (1) \mathcal{EO}_{a_6} = $\{x \mid x \in [0, 1]\}$; (2) er_{a_6} = 'is greater than'
- \mathcal{FRS}_{a_6} : (1) \mathcal{FO}_{a_6} = $\{x \mid x \in [0, 1]\}$; (2) fr_{a_6} = '>'
- The measure $\mu_{a_6}: \mathcal{EO}_{a_6} \rightarrow \mathcal{FO}_{a_6}$ is $\mu_{a_6}(x) = x$

a₇ AvailableSpace

- \mathcal{ERS}_{a_7} : (1) \mathcal{EO}_{a_7} = $\{x \mid x \in \mathbb{N}\}$; (2) er_{a_7} = 'is greater than'
- \mathcal{FRS}_{a_7} : (1) \mathcal{FO}_{a_7} = $\{x \mid x \in \mathbb{N}\}$; (2) fr_{a_7} = '>'
- The measure $\mu_{a_7}: \mathcal{EO}_{a_7} \rightarrow \mathcal{FO}_{a_7}$ is $\mu_{a_7}(x) = x$

a₈ DataAvailability

- \mathcal{ERS}_{a_8} : (1) $\mathcal{EO}_{a_8} = \{x \mid x \in [0, 1]\}$; (2) $er_{a_8} = \text{'is greater than'}$
- \mathcal{FRS}_{a_8} : (1) $\mathcal{FO}_{a_8} = \{x \mid x \in [0, 1]\}$; (2) $fr_{a_8} = \text{'>'}$
- The measure $\mu_{a_8} : \mathcal{EO}_{a_8} \rightarrow \mathcal{FO}_{a_8}$ is $\mu_{a_8}(x) = x$

a₉ Bandwidth

- \mathcal{ERS}_{a_9} : (1) $\mathcal{EO}_{a_9} = \{x \mid x \in \mathbb{N}\}$; (2) $er_{a_9} = \text{'is greater than'}$
- \mathcal{FRS}_{a_9} : (1) $\mathcal{FO}_{a_9} = \{x \mid x \in \mathbb{N}\}$; (2) $fr_{a_9} = \text{'>'}$
- The measure $\mu_{a_9} : \mathcal{EO}_{a_9} \rightarrow \mathcal{FO}_{a_9}$ is $\mu_{a_9}(x) = x$

a₁₀ RoundTripTime

- $\mathcal{ERS}_{a_{10}}$: (1) $\mathcal{EO}_{a_{10}} = \{x \mid x \in \mathbb{N}\}$; (2) $er_{a_{10}} = \text{'is greater than'}$
- $\mathcal{FRS}_{a_{10}}$: (1) $\mathcal{FO}_{a_{10}} = \{x \mid x \in \mathbb{N}\}$; (2) $fr_{a_{10}} = \text{'>'}$
- The measure $\mu_{a_{10}} : \mathcal{EO}_{a_{10}} \rightarrow \mathcal{FO}_{a_{10}}$ is $\mu_{a_{10}}(x) = x$

a₁₁ Membership in the source domain of a Network Service ns

- $\mathcal{ERS}_{a_{11}}$: (1) $\mathcal{EO}_{a_{11}} = \{x \mid x \text{ is a network domain}\}$; (2) $er_{a_{11}} = \text{'is equal to'}$
- $\mathcal{FRS}_{a_{11}}$: (1) $\mathcal{FO}_{a_{11}} = \{\text{member, non member}\}$; (2) $fr_{a_{11}} = \text{'='}$
- The measure $\mu_{a_{11}} : \mathcal{EO}_{a_{11}} \rightarrow \mathcal{FO}_{a_{11}}$ is:

$$\mu_{a_{11}}(x) = \begin{cases} \text{member} & \text{if } x = \text{ns.SourceDomain} \\ \text{non member} & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$$

a₁₂ Membership in the destination domain of a Network Service ns

- $\mathcal{ERS}_{a_{12}}$: (1) $\mathcal{EO}_{a_{12}} = \{x \mid x \text{ is a network domain}\}$; (2) $er_{a_{12}} = \text{'is equal to'}$
- $\mathcal{FRS}_{a_{12}}$: (1) $\mathcal{FO}_{a_{12}} = \{\text{member, non member}\}$; (2) $fr_{a_{12}} = \text{'='}$
- The measure $\mu_{a_{12}} : \mathcal{EO}_{a_{12}} \rightarrow \mathcal{FO}_{a_{12}}$ is:

$$\mu_{a_{12}}(x) = \begin{cases} \text{member} & \text{if } x = \text{ns.DestinationDomain} \\ \text{non member} & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$$

2.2 Execution Phase

In the execution phase, access to the measured values of available Grid services should be available and a user request should be considered. As regards the former, it is assumed that the measured values are collected and available for evaluation and decision making, whilst as regards the latter an example of user request is presented.

2.2.1 User Expected Satisfaction

Let us consider a user that requires a computing service offering the Scientific Linux operating system, but is also willing to accept Debian with lower satisfaction. The user then requires an IA32 (Intel Architecture 32 bit) processor family. The application is expected to store permanent data for around 220 GB in a storage service. A network service with around 70 Mbit/s of bandwidth and a small RTT (Round Trip Time) is desirable. Finally, the minimization of the waiting time of the computing service is optional.

a₁ OSType

- The elementary criterion of satisfaction $f_{a_1} : \mathcal{FO}_{a_1} \rightarrow [0, 1]$ is:

$$f_{a_1}(y) = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } y = 0 \\ 0.8 & \text{if } y = 1 \\ 0 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$$

a₂ ProcessorFamily

- The elementary criterion of satisfaction $f_{a_2} : \mathcal{FO}_{a_2} \rightarrow [0, 1]$ is:

$$f_{a_2}(y) = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } y = 0 \\ 0 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$$

a₅ FreeJobSlots

- The elementary criterion of satisfaction $f_{a_5} : \mathcal{FO}_{a_5} \rightarrow [0, 1]$ is:

$$f_{a_5}(y) = \frac{y}{slot_{max}}$$

where $slot_{max} \in \mathcal{FO}_{a_5}$ is the maximum number of job slots configured for the computing service.

a₇ AvailableSpace

- The elementary criterion of satisfaction $f_{a_7} : \mathcal{FO}_{a_7} \rightarrow [0, 1]$ is:

$$f_{a_7}(y) = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } y > 240 \\ \frac{y}{40} - 5 & \text{if } 200 \leq y \leq 240 \\ 0 & \text{if } y < 200 \end{cases}$$

a₉ Bandwidth

- The elementary criterion of satisfaction $f_{a_9} : \mathcal{FO}_{a_9} \rightarrow [0, 1]$ is (where: $SD = ns.SourceDomain$ and $DD = ns.DestinationDomain$):

$$f_{a_9}(y) = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } (y > 90) \text{ or } (SD = DD) \\ \frac{y}{40} - \frac{5}{4} & \text{if } 50 \leq y \leq 90 \\ 0 & \text{if } y < 50 \end{cases}$$

a₁₀ RoundTripTime

- The elementary criterion of satisfaction $f_{a_{10}} : \mathcal{FO}_{a_{10}} \rightarrow [0, 1]$ is:

$$f_{a_{10}}(y) = \begin{cases} 1 - \frac{y}{10} & \text{if } y \leq 10 \\ 0 & \text{if } y > 10 \end{cases}$$

a₁₁ Membership in the source domain of a Network Service ns

- The elementary criterion of satisfaction $f_{a_{11}} : \mathcal{FO}_{a_{11}} \rightarrow [0, 1]$ is:

$$f_{a_{11}}(y) = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } y = \text{member} \\ 0 & \text{if } y = \text{non member} \end{cases}$$

a₁₂ Membership in the destination domain of a Network Service ns

- The elementary criterion of satisfaction $f_{a_{12}} : \mathcal{FO}_{a_{12}} \rightarrow [0, 1]$ is:

$$f_{a_{12}}(y) = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } y = \text{member} \\ 0 & \text{if } y = \text{non member} \end{cases}$$

The user also defines the relevance relation \sim_{REL} as follows. The essential attributes are: (a_1) OSType, the application must be executed only in the specific operating systems; (a_2) ProcessorFamily, the application must run on a specific processor family; (a_7) AvailableSpace, the application is estimated to produce a certain amount of output data therefore the storage service

Figure 4. An instance of the general pattern applied to the use case

must provide sufficient space; (a_{10}) `cs.DomainURI` and (a_{11}) `ss.DomainURI`, the considered network services are those connecting from the domain of the computing service to the domain of the storage service. The desired attributes are: (a_9) `Bandwidth`, the final output of the job should be transferred on a link with around 70 Mb/s of bandwidth; (a_{10}) `RoundTripTime`, a small round trip time is desirable. The optional attribute is: (a_5) `FreeJobSlots`, a computing service with small response time is preferred.

Summarizing this discussion, the adopted relevance relation \sim_{REL} induces the following partition: (1) *essential* $\{a_1 \rightarrow e_{11}, a_2 \rightarrow e_{12}, a_7 \rightarrow e_{13}, a_{10} \rightarrow e_{14}, a_{11} \rightarrow e_{15}\}$, (2) *desired* $\{a_9 \rightarrow e_{21}, a_{10} \rightarrow e_{22}\}$ and (3) *optional* $\{a_4 \rightarrow e_{31}\}$.

2.2.2 Satisfaction Evaluation

The evaluation step consists in considering all possible meaningful tuples (CS, NS, SS) and in performing the evaluation of the indicator (global score) according to the proposed analysis method. This step requires both the attribute values and the user expectations. On the basis of the synthesized indicator, the possible solutions can be ranked and the decision about the resources to be assigned to the user can be meaningfully performed.

The aggregation pattern for our use case is presented in Figure 4. It implies an equation that is a compound weighted power mean presented in the following part by breaking it in partial results in order to facilitate the reading (see Equations 3 ($w_{11} = 0.2$; $w_{12} = 0.2$, $w_{13} = 0.2$; $w_{14} = 0.2$; $w_{15} = 0.2$; $w_{21} = 0.5$; $w_{22} = 0.5$; $w_{31} = 1$; $w_1 = 0.7$; $w_2 = 0.3$; $w_3 = 0.6$; $w_4 = 0.3$):

$$\begin{aligned}
 E_{ess} &= \left(w_{11}e_{11}^{-0.61} + w_{12}e_{12}^{-0.61} + w_{13}e_{13}^{-0.61} + w_{14}e_{14}^{-0.61} + w_{15}e_{15}^{-0.61} \right)^{-\frac{1}{0.67}} \\
 E_{des} &= \left(w_{21}e_{21}^{-0.72} + w_{22}e_{22}^{-0.72} \right)^{-\frac{1}{0.26}} \\
 E_{opt} &= \left(w_{31}e_{31} \right) \\
 E_1 &= \left((1 - w_1)E_{opt} + w_1E_{des} \right) \\
 E_2 &= \left((1 - w_2)E_1^{-0.72} + w_2E_{des}^{-0.72} \right)^{-\frac{1}{0.72}} \\
 E_3 &= \left((1 - w_3)E_2 + w_3E_{ess} \right) \\
 E &= \left((1 - w_4)E_3^{-0.72} + w_4E_{ess}^{-0.72} \right)^{-\frac{1}{0.72}} \tag{3}
 \end{aligned}$$

The parameters of the final aggregation function have been determined complying with the dis-

Figure 5. Behaviour of the aggregation function

cussion given in Section 1.2.

2.3 Behaviour of the Aggregation Function

In this section, an analysis of the behaviour of the aggregation function in Equation 3 is presented in order to show how the desired aggregation logic is properly synthesized (for an analysis of the assessment errors in LSP see [DF04a, DF04b]). The global satisfaction E is obtained by a multi-dimensional function in which inputs (i.e., the elementary satisfactions) have been partitioned in three categories. In order to show how variables in different categories affect E , the following method is proposed:

1. A representative for each category is selected (e.g., the satisfaction e_{11} concerning the OSType attribute for the essential category, the satisfaction e_{21} concerning the Bandwidth attribute for the desired category and the satisfaction e_{31} concerning the FreeJobSlots attribute for the optional category)
2. All possible couples are identified: $\{(e_{11}, e_{21}), (e_{11}, e_{31}), (e_{21}, e_{31})\}$; for each of them a diagram is drawn by maintaining all the other satisfaction values equal to 1

In Figure 5, diagrams showing how the global satisfaction is affected by the identified couples are presented. In particular, it is possible to appreciate the relationship between E and (e_{11}, e_{21}) , (e_{11}, e_{31}) , (e_{21}, e_{31}) respectively. Considering the essential satisfaction e_{11} , we would expect to observe that its satisfaction strongly affects E . In fact, in both diagrams (a) and (b), when the essential satisfaction is near 0, E is small apart from the value of the other satisfactions. For the same value of e_{11} , it can be also observed that the desired satisfaction e_{21} in (a) compared to the optional satisfaction e_{31} in (b) provides a more significant contribution to E . Considering diagram (c), since all essential satisfactions are equal to 1, E maintains a high value. Finally, as expected, the desired satisfaction e_{21} contributes more significantly than the optional satisfaction e_{31} .

3 Summary

In this chapter, the first contribution of this work has been presented, that is, a method for selecting Grid services based on the quality requirements expressed by the user. This method proposes a rigorous modelling of features of the resources that can be subject of a user request. By means of such features, the user can express individual subjective satisfactions and can also identify and differentiate relevances. The method enables the synthesis of a global satisfaction degree that can be used to compare different proposal and consequently select the best. In the next part, the second main contribution of this work is presented, that is, a mapping of this method into a query language able to work on XML-based representation of Grid resources.

Part IV
A Language for Quality-Based Selection

Chapter 10

The XMatch Language

In this chapter, the XMatch language enabling to express queries over XML-based representations of Grid resources is presented, considering also the satisfaction degree that a user perceives as regards the possible values of the attributes of interest [ACMM05b, AMM05]. Two use cases are provided in order to exemplify how the language can be applied in meaningful scenarios concerning Grid systems. In Appendix 12, the complete grammar is given. The grammar rules are given only for symbols starting with the prefix `XM`, whilst the other symbols are taken from the XQuery W3C specification [BCF⁺05].

1 The Main Clause

The core part of the XMatch language is an expression defined in the grammar by the symbol `XMExpr` as follows:

Example 2

```
XMExpr ::= XMForClause XMLetClause+ XMWhereClause XMReturnClause
```

The rule defining this symbol is inspired by the FLWOR (For-Let-Where-Order by-Return) expression of the XQuery language [BCF⁺05]. The first clause of this expression generates an ordered sequence of tuples of bound variables called the tuple stream (`XMForClause`). For each set of bound variables generated in this step, the second clause (`XMLetClause`) enables to bind one or more variables to the value returned by an elementary criterion of satisfaction as regards elements belonging to the tuple stream. The third clause (`XMWhereClause`) enables the association of each variable defined in the second clause (i.e., an elementary satisfaction) with a relevance category, thereby defining the aggregation pattern. The fourth and last clause (`XMReturnClause`) is used to return the result as an XML document and allows the selection of a subset of solutions based on their overall satisfaction.

2 Generation of the Tuple Stream

As stated in the previous section, the clause `XMForClause` generates an ordered sequence of tuples of bound variables, called the tuple stream. This is a simplified version of the XQuery `ForClause`, where only the basic constructs are maintained to select elements from an XML document and to generate the streams of the possible solutions by using the join capability. For each XMatch expression, only one `XMForClause` is allowed with one or more variables to be bound to different types of nodes. The `URILiteral` is defined in the XQuery specification and should refer to a URI that can be resolved to a file containing the data in XML format from which the set of important fragments is extracted. The `OrExpr` is also part of the XQuery specification.

Example 3

```

XMForClause ::= <"for" "$" VarName "in" XMDocCall
              ( "," "$" VarName "in" XMDocCall ) *
XMDocCall   ::= "doc(" URILiteral ")" XMPPathExpr? XMPredicate?
XMPPathExpr ::= ( "/" QName ) * ( "/" "@" QName ) ?
XMPredicate ::= "[" OrExpr "]"

```

3 Expressing the Satisfaction

In this section, we describe the symbol `XMLetClause` as the essential construct for defining a single elementary criterion of satisfaction. The three main categories are supported (see Section 1.1): an enumeration of all possible values returned by a measurement of an attribute, an absolute ranking of these values and a relative ranking [Duj96].

Example 4

```

XMLetClause ::= "let" ( "$" VarName "!=" ( XMSimpleEnum | XMCompEnum | XMRange ) )
XMSimpleEnum ::= XMPPathExpr ValueComp XMLElement "satisfies" XMSatLiteral
                ( "," XMLElement "satisfies" XMSatLiteral ) *
XMCompEnum   ::= XMPPathExprList ValueComp XMLElementList "satisfies"
                XMSatLiteral ( "," XMLElementList "satisfies" XMSatLiteral ) *
XMRange      ::= XMPPathExpr "in" XMLElement "to" XMLElement "satisfies"
                ( "with" "linear" "increment" | "with" "linear" "decrement"
                  | "with" "around" | "not" "around" )
XMPPathExprList ::= ( " XMPPathExpr ( "," XMPPathExpr ) + " )
XMLElementList  ::= ( " XMLElement ( "," XMLElement ) + " )
XMLElement      ::= ( Literal | XMPPathExpr | XMAggregation )
XMSatLiteral    ::= ( "0"? "." Digits | "1" )
XMAggregation   ::= ( "max" | "min" | "avg" | "sum" | "count" )
XMPPathExpr     ::= ( "/" QName ) * ( "/" "@" QName ) ?

```

The values that are input for an elementary criterion of satisfaction are determined by a simplified XPath expression (`XMPPathExpr`). A step in this expression consists only of a child forward step in its abbreviated form with a name node test according to the definitions given in the XPath 2.0 specification [BBC⁺05a]. As stated in this specification, the result of an XPath expression is any sequence allowed by the data model. An important characteristic introduced by the new data model [FMM⁺05] is that there is no distinction between an item (i.e., a node or an atomic value) and a singleton sequence containing this item (an item is equivalent to a singleton sequence containing the item and vice versa). As regards XMatch, only a sequence of atomic values is admitted as a result of an `XMPPathExpr` expression. Besides, it must be specified how an elementary criterion of satisfaction is applied to such a type of result. Given the simplified path expression, the resulting sequence is composed by elements with the same qualified name at the same distance from the root node.

The elementary criteria of satisfaction when the result of a path expression is a singleton is described. The first category of elementary criteria of satisfaction can be used when the number of possible values for which the user wants to express an explicit satisfaction is finite. For instance, a user may want to express a number of acceptable possibilities for the operating system type where its job should be executed; the most preferred one is `Scientific Linux`, but `RedHat Enterprise Linux` is acceptable with lower satisfaction. This could be expressed as in Example 5 by using the `XMSimpleEnum` clause.

Example 5

```

let $sel := $CS/OSName eq "Scientific Linux" satisfies 1,
          "RedHat Enterprise Edition" satisfies 0.8

```

A more complex use case supported in XMatch is the association of an elementary satisfaction by enumeration to a compound comparison predicate. For instance, if a user wants to express a satisfaction associated to both the name and version of an operating system, this can be done as in Example 6 by using the `XMCompEnum` clause.

Example 6

```

let $sel := ($CS/OSName, $CS/OSVersion) eq ("Scientific Linux", "3") satisfies 1,
           ("RedHat Enterprise Edition", "3") satisfies 0.8

```


Figure 1. The four continuous linear elementary criteria of satisfactions supported in XMatch

The second category of elementary criteria of satisfaction can be used when the expression of satisfaction is based on parameters independent from attribute values under investigation. The possible functions that map the range of values into a satisfaction are infinite. It has been chosen to express in the language four meaningful functions. These are linear and capture an increasing satisfaction, a decreasing satisfaction, a full satisfaction centered around a value and a null satisfaction centered around a value (see Figure 1). An example of usage for the first function (linear increment) would be a user requiring a storage service with at least 50 GB of available disk space. Values up to 70 GB produce an increasing satisfaction, whilst values greater than 70 GB are considered to be equal and fully satisfying. This can be captured in XMatch as in Example 7 by using the XMRRange clause. The satisfaction is 0 if the value of the attribute is lower than or equal to the lower bound of the range, whilst it is 1 if the value of the attribute is equal to or higher than the upper bound.

Example 7

```
let $e2 := $SS/FreeSpace in 50 to 70 satisfies with linear increment
```

The second linear function (linear decrement) is similar to the previous function, except that for values lower than or equal to the lower bound, the satisfaction is 1 and for values equal to or higher than the upper bound, the satisfaction is 0. For attribute values in the range, the satisfaction linearly decreases. For instance, let us consider a user that is fully satisfied if the response time of a service is lower than or equal to 5 ms, but will accept values up to 30 ms (see Example 8).

Example 8

```
let $e3 := $CS/EstimatedResponseTime in 5 to 30 satisfies with linear decrement
```

The third function should be used when a high satisfaction is associated to values close to that reputed to be the optimum. For instance, let us consider a user requiring a service which price is around around 20 €/day with a 10% tolerance (see Example 9).

Example 9

```
let $e4 := $Service/DayPrice in 18 to 22 satisfies with around
```

The last function should be used when a null satisfaction is given by a certain value and low satisfactions are provided by values close to this.

The third category of elementary criteria of satisfaction refers to a relative comparison amongst the attribute values of all entities in the evaluation context. This criterion requires the introduction of aggregation functions (e.g., min or max). They can be used in both the first and second elementary criteria of satisfaction given above. For instance, let us consider a user requiring the storage service offering the highest free storage capacity (see Example 10).

Example 10

```
let $e5 := $$S/FreeSpace eq max satisfies 1
```

As a design choice, the function is identified by a literal and the argument to which it applies is the one subject of the elementary criterion (implicit argument, `$$S/FreeSpace` in the example). The use case of a relative ranking concerning a range of values can be expressed by enabling the possibility of using aggregation functions to define the range bounds. For instance, a user may be fully satisfied when he or she is assigned for the service with the lowest response time amongst those available, but his or her satisfaction linearly decreases up to 0 when the highest is given.

Example 11

```
let $e6 := $CS/EstimatedResponseTime in min($CS/EstimatedResponseTime)
to max($CS/EstimatedResponseTime) satisfies with linear decrement
```

In the Examples from 5 to 11, the hypothesis is that the path expression returns a singleton, whilst in the remaining part of this section, the behaviour of the `XMLetClause` is generalized to path expressions returning a sequence with multiple atomic values. In order to perform a meaningful evaluation of the satisfaction, the following definitions need to be introduced.

Definition 12 (Intra-evaluation relationship) *Two distinct elements el_1 and el_2 of an XML document are in intra-evaluation relationship if and only if the qualified name of el_1 is equal to the qualified name of el_2 and they are siblings.*

Definition 13 (Inter-evaluation relationship) *Two distinct elements el_1 and el_2 of an XML document are in inter-evaluation relationship if and only if they are not siblings and the path from the root to el_1 and the path from the root to el_2 are equal in terms of the qualified names of the nodes part of this path.*

According to the last definition, two elements in inter-evaluation relationship are identified by the same `XMPathExpr` expression, but they are not siblings. In order to exemplify the two definitions, let us consider the following example.

Example 12

```
1: <DataSet>
2:   <A>
3:     <B>
4:       <C>10</C>
5:       <C>2</C>
6:     </B>
7:     <B>
8:       <C>1</C>
9:     </B>
10:    <B>
11:      <C>2</C>
12:      <C>3</C>
13:    </B>
14:  </A>
15:  <A>
16:    <B>
17:      <C>7</C>
18:      <C>4</C>
19:    </B>
20:  </A>
```

```
21: </DataSet>
```

The path expression `/DataSet/A/B/C` returns a sequence with seven `C` elements. As an example in this sequence, the first and second element (lines 4 and 5) are in intra-evaluation relationship because they share the same parent node (line 3); the second and the third one (lines 5 and 8) are in inter-evaluation relationship because they have different parent nodes (lines 3 and 7 respectively), but are identified by the same path expression. Values in intra-evaluation relationships are considered as alternative values when determining the satisfaction concerning the attribute defined according to the service evaluation method (see Section 9). Therefore, the evaluation of an elementary criterion of satisfaction is made for each value and the higher satisfaction will be selected for the attribute under consideration. As regards values in inter-evaluation relationships, they are reputed to refer to different alternative entities according to the service evaluation method. Therefore, the evaluation of the global satisfaction must be based on only one entity amongst the alternative ones. Such an entity is selected maximizing the global satisfaction. In order to exemplify these concepts by the Example 12, let us consider a user requiring an `A` element. The user has a linearly increasing satisfaction from 0 to 1 for the values of `C` from 0 to 10. This elementary criterion can be written in XMatch as expressed in Example 13.

Example 13

```
let $e1 := $A/B/C in 0 to 10 satisfies with linear increment
```

By means of the `XMForClause`, the variable `$A` is bound to each `A` element in the document presented in the Example 12. Let us consider the first `A` element: according to Definition 12, the `C` elements in lines 4 and 5 are in an intra-evaluation relationship. The same relationship holds for the `C` elements in lines 11 and 12. For each subset of the elements that are in intra-evaluation relationship (i.e., 10 and 2 in lines 4 and 5; 1 in line 8; 2 and 3 in lines 11 and 12), a representative providing the maximum satisfaction is selected and returned as part of the sequence assigned to the `$e1` variable, that is (1, 0.1, 0.3). This demonstrates how the intra-evaluation relationships can be resolved within the single elementary criterion. According to Definition 13, the three satisfactions in the sequence refer to attributes that are in an inter-evaluation relationship. This implies that in order to select the satisfaction participating to the aggregation producing the global satisfaction, we need to relate the values returned by different elementary criteria of satisfaction considering also their relevance. A complete example is given in Section 6. Following the same rules, the elementary criterion applied to the second `A` element will bind the variable `$e1` with the singleton sequence (0.7).

4 Classifying the Satisfactions by Relevance

In this section, it is explained how the association of an elementary satisfaction to a relevance category is modelled in the XMatch language. Potentially, the relevance categories can be infinite, but only three of them are introduced as they are sufficient for meaningful use cases. They are defined in the XMatch language grammar by using the following string literals: `essential`, `desirable` and `optional`. The advantage of such a definition is the improvement of the legibility of XMatch queries. A possible approach to generalize the language to an high number of relevance classes is to use natural numbers to label the relevance categories: the lower the natural number associated to a relevance category, the more important the satisfaction.

Example 14

```
XMWhereClause ::= "where"
                ( ( XMRelevanceSubj ( "essential" | "desirable" | "optional" ) ) |
                  ( XMRelevanceSubj "essential" and XMRelevanceSubj "desirable" ) |
                  ( XMRelevanceSubj "essential" and XMRelevanceSubj "optional" ) |
                  ( XMRelevanceSubj "desirable" and XMRelevanceSubj "optional" ) |
                  ( XMRelevanceSubj "essential" and XMRelevanceSubj "desirable"
                    and XMRelevanceSubj "optional" ) )
XMRelevanceSubj ::= ( "$" VarName "is" | XMVarNameList "are" )
XMVarNameList  ::= ( " "$" VarName ( "," "$" VarName )+ " )"
```

Given a set of XMLetClause expressions defining elementary satisfactions, each of them can be associated to a relevance category by using the XMWhereClause (see Example 15). This provides the meaningful information for building the aggregation pattern.

Example 15

where (\$e1, \$e2) are essential and \$e3 is desirable

Weight and power parameters used in the aggregation pattern (see Figure 2) are considered to be part of the query processor. Let us consider Example 16 showing an XML document having elements in both intra- and inter-evaluation relationships.

Example 16

```

1: <DataSet>
2:   <A>
3:     <B>
4:       <C>10</C>
5:       <C>2</C>
6:       <D>6</D>
7:     </B>
8:   <B>
9:     <C>1</C>
10:  </B>
11:  <B>
12:    <C>2</C>
13:    <C>3</C>
14:    <D>9</D>
15:  </B>
16: </A>
17: <A>
18:   ...
19: </A>
20: </DataSet>

```

We consider a user that wants to select an A element for which it is essential that a C element is higher than 6 and it is desirable that a D element is higher than 8. These expectations can be written in XMatch as shown in the following example:

Example 17

```

for $A in doc("data.xml")/DataSet/A,
let $e1 := $A/B/C gt 6 satisfies 1
let $e2 := $A/B/D gt 8 satisfies 1
where $e1 is essential and $e2 is desirable

```

The values returned by the expression \$A/B/C are in both intra- and inter-evaluation relationships. The same condition holds for the values returned by the expression \$A/B/D. Considering the rules defined in Section 3, the variable \$e1 is bound to the sequence (1, 0, 0), whilst the variable \$e2 is bound to the sequence (0, 1). In order to choose the satisfaction participating in the aggregation for each elementary criterion of satisfaction, the ancestor relationship for performing such a choice is introduced. This relationship applies to the values of an XML document selected from two or more XMLetClause's and presented in Definition 14.

Definition 14 (Ancestor relationship) A value v_{ih} ($h \in (1, m)$) in the i -th sequence (v_{i1}, \dots, v_{im}) returned by a path expression $/X/Y$ (where X and Y are path expressions) is in an ancestor relationship with a value v_{jk} ($k \in (1, n)$) in the j -th sequence (v_{j1}, \dots, v_{jn}) returned by a path expression $/W/Z$ (where W and Z are path expressions) if and only if the path X is equal to the path W and the number of steps from the element v_{ih} to the element v_{jk} is equal to the number of steps in Y plus the number of steps in Z . If v_{ih} is in an ancestor relationship with v_{jk} , then the same relationship holds for their respective elementary satisfactions.

In order to exemplify this definition, the two path expressions in Example 17 ($/A/B/C$ and $/A/B/D$) applied to the XML document in Example 16 are considered. They identify the sequences (10, 2, 1, 2, 3) and (6, 9) respectively. Considering Definition 14, X is equal to $/A/B$, Y is equal to C , W is equal to $/A/B$ and Z is equal to D . The first and the second value of the

first sequence (i.e., 10 and 2) are in an ancestor relationship with the first value of the second sequence (i.e., 6), whilst they are not in an ancestor relationship with the second value (i.e., 9). For the final aggregation, only one value for each elementary criterion of satisfaction has to be selected. The choice is made by selecting the n -tuple of elementary satisfactions (n is the number of elementary criteria of satisfaction) that are in ancestor relationships and that maximize the global satisfaction. It may happen that it is not possible to produce a complete tuple because the structure of the XML document may lead to the identification of a set of elementary satisfactions that are in ancestor relationship whose cardinality is less than n . In this situation, the missing elementary satisfactions are considered to be equal to 0. In Example 17, we have two elementary criteria, therefore we must produce pairs of elementary satisfactions (i.e., $n = 2$). The sequence $e_1 = (1, 0, 0)$ associated to the sequence of values v_1 is composed of three values, whilst the sequence $e_2 = (0, 1)$ associated to the sequence of values v_2 is composed of two values. In particular, it can be pointed out that the second value of e_1 (i.e., $e_{12} = 0$) has no respective satisfaction in e_2 for which an ancestor relationship holds. Therefore, the related pair is $(e_{12}, -)$, where the symbol '-' expresses the lack of an elementary satisfaction (to be replaced with 0 during the aggregation phase). Summarizing, the tuple of elementary satisfactions that are candidate for the aggregation are: $(1, 0)$, $(0, -)$ and $(0, 1)$. The tuple that maximizes the global satisfaction is the first because its first value is essential and equal to 1.

5 Constructing the Result

In this section, it is described how the result of the query is constructed and returned. It was decided to define a clause that does not provide any transformation capability. The transformation of the result may be achieved by adding a postprocessing phase using languages like XQuery or XSLT. The `XMReturnClause` clause returns an XML document with a predefined structure as presented in Example 18.

Example 18

```
<Results>
  <Result E="0.98">
    ...
  </Result>
  <Result E="0.94">
    ...
  </Result>
</Results>
```

Each `Result` element contains a set of elements as generated by the `XMForClause` and an `E` attribute with the overall satisfaction associated to the solution. These elements are returned following a decreasing order with respect to the value of `E`. Moreover, the number of results can be limited in two ways: by asking the 'Top K ' results and by dropping all solutions that do not reach a minimum overall satisfaction.

Example 19

```
XMReturnClause ::= "return" "top" digits ( "with threshold" XMSatLiteral )?
```

6 Use Cases

In this chapter, two meaningful use cases of resource selection in the area of Grid computing are presented. They are described in terms of resource properties, potential user requirements, and selection by means of the `XMatch` language. The first use case refers to the selection of a set of three different Grid services that better satisfy the user expectations (see Section 6.1). The XML representation of these services is simplified in the sense that neither intra-evaluation nor inter-evaluation relationships are present. The second use case refers to the selection of a single storage service, but its structure is more complex and presents intra-evaluation, inter-evaluation and ancestor relationships (see Section 6.2).

6.1 Computing, Storage and Network Resources

A simplified scenario is considered where core services referring to computing, storage and network resources are defined as follows (see also Section 2): ‘computing service’ is as a uniquely identified Grid service that can provide a user software application for computing power in a certain execution environment; ‘storage service’ as a uniquely identified Grid service that manages a storage space; and ‘network service’ as a uniquely identified service that offers unidirectional communication capability between network domains that are meant as sets of services sharing the same connectivity [ACGV04]. The network service is considered as unidirectional because of the nature of the characterizing parameters (i.e., the achievable bandwidth from domain A to domain B can be different from the bandwidth from domain B to domain A).

The following XML fragments represent a computing, a storage and a network service. They are based on a schema and represent the mapping to a formal relational system. In a real scenario, a broker service maintains and continuously updates a cache with the representation of the available services [AAA⁺04]. The broker also receives requests from users and, based on their requirements and preferences, performs the matchmaking phase during which suitable solutions are prepared and one is selected.

Example 20

```
<data>
  <CS>
    <URI>https://hostname.cnaf.infn.it/CS</URI>
    <DomainURI>/INFN/CNAF</DomainURI>
    <Type>CS</Type>
    <OSName>Scientific Linux</OSName>
    <OSVersion>3.0.3</OSVersion>
    <ProcessorFamily>IA32</ProcessorFamily>
    <AssignedJobSlots>30</AssignedJobSlots>
    <WaitingJobs>10</WaitingJobs>
    <RunningJobs>30</RunningJobs>
    <FreeJobSlots>0</FreeJobSlots>
  </CS>
  <SS>
    <URI>https://hostname.mi.infn.it/SS</URI>
    <Type>SS</Type>
    <DomainURI>/INFN/MI</DomainURI>
    <Durability>0.6</Durability>
    <AvailableSpace Unit="GB">300</AvailableSpace>
    <DataAvailability>0.8</DataAvailability>
  </SS>
  <NS>
    <URI>/NS/1</URI>
    <Type>NS</Type>
    <SourceDomainURI>/INFN/CNAF</SourceDomainURI>
    <DestDomainURI>/INFN/MI</DestDomainURI>
    <Bandwidth Unit="Mb/s">300</Bandwidth>
    <RoundTripTime Unit="ms">3</RoundTripTime>
  </NS>
</data>
```

Let us consider a user that requires a computing service offering the Scientific Linux operating system in its version 3.0.3, but also Debian Linux version 3.1 is acceptable with lower satisfaction. Then, the user requires an IA32 processor family. The application is expected to store permanent data for around 220 GB in a storage service. A network service with around 70 Mbit/s of bandwidth and a small RTT (Round Trip Time) is desirable. Finally, the minimization of the waiting time of the computing service is optional. In Example 21, a possible XMatch query expressing these requirements is shown.

Example 21

```
for $NS in doc("data.xml")/data/NS,
  $CS in doc("data.xml")/data/CS[DomainURI=$NS/SourceDomainURI]
  $SS in doc("data.xml")/data/SS[DomainURI=$NS/DestDomainURI]
let $e1 := ($CS/OSName, $CS/OSVersion) eq ("Scientific Linux", "3.03") satisfies 1,
  ("Debian Linux", "3.1") satisfies 0.8
let $e2 := $CS/ProcessorFamily eq "IA32" satisfies 1
let $e3 := $SS/AvailableSpace in 200 to 250 satisfies with linear increment
let $e4 := $NS/Bandwidth in 50 to 100 satisfies with linear increment
let $e5 := $NS/RoundTripTime in 0 to 10 satisfies with linear decrement
```


Figure 2. Example aggregation pattern given by the XMWhereClause

```

let $e6 := $CS/FreeJobSlots in 0 to max satisfies with linear increment
where ($e1, $e2, $e3) are essential and ($e4, $e5) are desirable and $e6 is optional
return top 10 with threshold 0.6

```

Each let clause is used to express an elementary criterion of satisfaction, whilst the where clause describes the aggregation pattern in Figure 2 and corresponds to the following equation of our service evaluation model:

$$\begin{aligned}
E_{ess} &= \left(w_{11}e_1^{r_{ess}} + w_{12}e_2^{r_{ess}} + w_{13}e_3^{r_{ess}} \right)^{\frac{1}{r_{ess}}} \\
E_{des} &= \left(w_{21}e_4^{r_{des}} + w_{22}e_6^{r_{des}} \right)^{\frac{1}{r_{des}}} \\
E_{opt} &= e_5 \\
E_1 &= \left((1 - w_1)E_{opt} + w_1E_{des} \right) \\
E_2 &= \left((1 - w_2)E_1^{r_{aggr}} + w_2E_{des}^{r_{aggr}} \right)^{\frac{1}{r_{aggr}}} \\
E_3 &= \left((1 - w_3)E_2 + w_3E_{ess} \right) \\
E &= \left((1 - w_4)E_3^{r_{aggr}} + w_4E_{ess}^{r_{aggr}} \right)^{\frac{1}{r_{aggr}}} \tag{1}
\end{aligned}$$

6.2 Storage Element

In this section, a scenario concerning a user interested in selecting a storage service is considered. The expected characteristics of this service are: the access protocol must be `gridftp` (`/SS/AccessProtocol/Type` element); the data availability should be as high as possible (`/SS/SA/DataAvailability` element); the storage area must be of a permanent type and with an available space greater than 60 GB (`/SS/SA/AvailableSpace` and `/SS/SA/Type` elements); the user must be able to access the storage area, that is, the virtual organization (VO) he or she belongs to (`urn:vo:1`) must be authorized (`/SS/SA/AuthorizedVO` element). The following XML document represents two examples of storage services:

Example 22

```

1: <data>
2:   <SS>
3:     <UniqueID>urn:cnaf.infn.it:storage.service</URI>
4:     <SA>
5:       <LocalID>storage.area.001</LocalID>
6:       <AvailableSpace>70</AvailableSpace>
7:       <AuthorizedVO>urn:vo:1</AuthorizedVO>
8:       <AuthorizedVO>urn:vo:2</AuthorizedVO>
9:       <Type>permanent</Type>
10:      <DataAvailability>0.7</DataAvailability>
11:    </SA>
12:    <SA>
13:      <LocalID>storage.area.002</LocalID>
14:      <AvailableSpace>90</AvailableSpace>

```

```

15:         <Type>permanent</Type>
16:         <AuthorizedVO>urn:vo:3</AuthorizedVO>
17:     </SA>
18:     <SA>
19:         <LocalID>storage.area.003</LocalID>
20:         <AvailableSpace>50</AvailableSpace>
21:         <Type>volatile</Type>
22:         <DataAvailability>0.7</DataAvailability>
23:         <AuthorizedVO>urn:vo:4</AuthorizedVO>
24:         <AuthorizedVO>urn:vo:5</AuthorizedVO>
25:     </SA>
26:     <AccessProtocol>
27:         <URI>gridftp://grid001.cnaf.infn.it:2811</URI>
28:         <Type>gridftp</Type>
29:     </AccessProtocol>
30: </SS>
31: <SS>
32:     <UniqueID>urn:cern.ch:storage.service</URI>
33:     <SA>
34:         <LocalID>storage.area.001</LocalID>
35:         <AvailableSpace>30</AvailableSpace>
36:         <Type>permanent</Type>
37:         <DataAvailability>0.9</DataAvailability>
38:         <AuthorizedVO>urn:vo:4</AuthorizedVO>
39:         <AuthorizedVO>urn:vo:5</AuthorizedVO>
40:     </SA>
41:     <SA>
42:         <LocalID>storage.area.001</LocalID>
43:         <AvailableSpace>80</AvailableSpace>
44:         <Type>permanent</Type>
45:         <DataAvailability>0.9</DataAvailability>
46:         <AuthorizedVO>urn:vo:1</AuthorizedVO>
47:     </SA>
48:     <AccessProtocol>
49:         <URI>gridftp://grid005.cern.ch:2811</URI>
50:         <Type>gridftp</Type>
51:     </AccessProtocol>
52: </SS>
53: </data>

```

The following is an XMatch query expressing the user expectations in the use case presented in Example 22:

Example 23

```

for $SS in doc("data.xml")/data/SS
let $e1 := $SS/SA/AuthorizedVO eq "urn:vo:1" satisfies 1
let $e2 := $SS/SA/AvailableSpace gt 60 satisfies 1
let $e3 := $SS/SA/Type eq "permanent" satisfies 1
let $e4 := $SS/SA/DataAvailability in 0 to 1 satisfies with linear increment
let $e5 := $SS/AccessProtocol/Type eq "gridftp" satisfies 1
where ( $e1, $e2, $e3, $e5 ) are essential and $e4 is desired
return top 10 with threshold 0.6

```

For each storage service in the XML document, the five elementary criteria of satisfaction are applied to the five attributes of interest. According to the Definitions 12, 13 and 14, we may note that intra-evaluation relationships hold amongst the elements returned by the path expression $\$SS/SA/AuthorizedVO$, whilst inter-evaluation and ancestor relationships hold amongst the elements returned by the path expressions $\$SS/SA/AuthorizedVO$, $\$SS/SA/AvailableSpace$, $\$SS/SA/Type$ and $\$SS/SA/DataAvailability$.

For the first storage service (from line 2 to line 30), the XMLletClause's generate the following sequences of satisfaction: $e_1 = (1, 0, 0)$, $e_2 = (1, 1, 0)$, $e_3 = (1, 1, 0)$, $e_4 = (1, 0)$ and $e_5 = (1)$. The tuples of elementary satisfactions that are candidate for the aggregation are: $(1, 1, 1, 1, 1)$, $(0, 1, 1, -, 1)$ and $(0, 0, 0, 0, 1)$. From these three candidate tuples, the first is selected in order to determine the global satisfaction. For the second storage service (from line 31 to line 52), the XMLletClause's generate the following sequences of satisfaction: $e_1 = (0, 1)$, $e_2 = (0, 1)$, $e_3 = (1, 1)$, $e_4 = (0.9, 0.9)$ and $e_5 = (1)$. The tuples of elementary satisfactions that are candidate for the aggregation are $(0, 0, 1, 0.9, 1)$ and $(1, 1, 1, 0.9, 1)$. The second candidate tuple is selected in order to determine the global satisfaction.

Summarizing, the representative tuple of satisfactions for the first storage service is $(1, 1, 1, 1, 1)$, whilst the representative tuple of satisfactions for the second storage service is $(1, 1, 1, 0.9, 1)$. Be-

cause of the monotonicity of the weighted power mean [Bul03], we can assert that the first storage service will be selected as it provides the highest satisfaction amongst the considered services. The XMatch query given in Example 23 also has a representation in terms of an aggregation function as for the previous use case (see Equation 3 and Figure 2).

7 Summary

This chapter introduced XMatch, a language inspired by XQuery that supports the service evaluation method introduced in the previous part. The various clauses of the language have been motivated and described, and further suitable examples have been given. In the last part, two important use cases in the area of Grid system have been presented. The purpose was to exemplify the usage and benefits of the XMatch language for expressing the user satisfaction as regards values related to characteristics of Grid resources to be assigned to its processes. The provided details can also serve to understand the potential issues for an implementation phase.

Chapter 11

Rewriting XMatch into XQuery

This chapter is dedicated to the definition and demonstration of an approach for rewriting XMatch queries into the XQuery language. This enables experiments to be performed, using the available XQuery engines. Section 1 is dedicated to the description of this approach, whilst Section 2 provides a complete example.

1 Approach

In this section, an approach to rewrite XMatch queries in terms of XQuery is presented. The four main XMatch clauses are analyzed, and it is described how they can be translated into XQuery. We start from the `XMForClause` (see Section 2). This clause is used to generate a stream of the possible solutions to be evaluated. It enables the definition of an inner join between several complex elements part of an XML document. The grammar rules defining this clause are a subset of the XQuery ones, therefore it may be asserted that valid XMatch expressions are also valid XQuery expressions.

The `XMLetClause` (see Section 3) is used to specify the several elementary criteria of satisfaction. Each elementary criterion of satisfaction should be applied to the result of an `XMPathExpr` expression in respect of the three relationships given in Definitions 12, 13 and 14. The three definitions are used to verify a locality property amongst elements to be used to build the appropriate solutions. In particular, the intra-evaluation relationship (Definition 12) is used to state that each elementary criterion of satisfaction should be evaluated against the only sibling values identified by an `XMPathExpr` expression. If there are several subsets of siblings, then they should participate to different possible solutions.

The inter-evaluation relationship (Definition 13) is used to state that the aggregation of elementary satisfactions about sibling elements with different qualified names (e.g., `$A/B/C` and `$A/B/D`) should be performed in the context of their common parent. If many combination exist, then the possible solutions should be generated.

Considering the tree in Figure 1 to represent an XML document, `/A/B[1]/C` should be evaluated together with `/A/B[1]/D` and `/A/B[2]/C` should be evaluated together with `/A/B[2]/D`. The numbers in square brackets identify the ordinal position of the element amongst those identified by the XPath expression. For instance, `/A/B[2]` identifies the second B element that is a child of the element `/A`.

The ancestor relationship (Definition 14) is used to state that the aggregation of elementary satisfactions about elements that are not siblings (e.g., `$A/B/F` and `$A/B/G/H`) should be performed in the context of their closest common ancestor. If many combinations exist, then the possible solutions should be generated (e.g., `$A/B[1]/F` should be evaluated together with `$A/B[1]/G/H`, `$A/B[2]/F` should be evaluated together with `$A/B[2]/G/H`) (see Figure 2). Considering the XQuery language, there are many possibilities to enforce these relationships and generate valid solutions of elementary satisfactions to be aggregated. Let us start from the an-

Figure 1. A tree representing an XML document (in each node, the left symbol is the element QName and the symbol is the value element value)

Figure 2. A tree representing an XML document (in each node, the left symbol is the element QName and the symbol is the value element value)

cestor relationship. In order to evaluate whether two elements identified by two different path expressions hold this relationship, we need to measure two characteristics expressed in Definitions 15 and 16.

Definition 15 (Distance between two elements) Let us consider an XML document D and two elements x and y identified by the X and Y path expressions respectively. We define the function $\text{dist}(x, y)$ as the distance between x and y in terms of the minimum number of nodes that must be traversed in order to go from one element to the other in the document D .

Definition 16 (Shortest distance) Let us consider two path expressions X and Y . We define the function $\text{sp-dist}(X, Y)$ as the shortest possible distance between two elements x and y that could be identified by X and Y respectively.

Given the two definitions above, we can rewrite the ancestor relationship in terms of them as follows:

Definition 17 (Ancestor relationship) Let us consider an XML document D and two elements x and y identified by the X and Y path expressions respectively. The elements x and y are in ancestor relationship if and only if $\text{dist}(x, y) = \text{sp-dist}(X, Y)$.

For instance, let us consider the tree structure of an XML document represented in Figure 2. The path expressions $X = /A/B/F$ and $Y = /A/B/G/H$, and the elements $x = /A[1]/B[1]/F[1]$ and $y = /A[1]/B[2]/G[1]/H[1]$, then $\text{dist}(x, y) = 4$. This can be verified considering that in order to go from element x to element y , firstly, we need to traverse $B[1]$, then we reach the

root $A[1]$, after that we descend to $B[2]$ and finally we traverse $G[1]$. As regards the shortest possible distance, $sp\text{-}dist(X, Y) = 2$. This can be verified as follows: in order to go from the x element to the y element, we must firstly traverse B , then we traverse G . In the example given above, the two elements x and y are not in ancestor relationship because $dist(x, y) \neq sp\text{-}dist(X, Y)$.

The implementations of the functions given in Definition 15 and Definition 16 in terms of XQuery are provided in Listing 1 and Listing 2 respectively. In the computation of the distance, they also include the starting and ending nodes because they will be used by providing as input arguments the parent nodes of the actual elements to be considered. This assumption enables the appropriate management of the case where in a `XMLetClause` focusing on elements returned by the path expression X the following situation occurs: the path expression $X/. .$ identifies nodes that are leaves, that is, there are missing values that should be returned by the path expression X and the respective elementary satisfaction of which should be 0 (see Section 4).

Listing 1

```
declare function xm:dist($x as node(), $y as node()) as xs:integer {
  let $x-ancestors := $x/ancestor-or-self::element(),
      $y-ancestors := $y/ancestor-or-self::element()
  return count($x-ancestors)+count($y-ancestors)
        +1-2*count($x-ancestors intersect $y-ancestors)
};
```

The proposed implementation of the `dist()` function uses the `ancestor-or-self` axis which identifies the context node and the ancestors of the context node. By using the `intersect` operator, we can identify the nodes that are common to both sequences, being thus able to compute the distance as defined in Listing 1.

Listing 2

```
declare function xm:sp-dist($x as node()+, $y as node()+) as
xs:integer {
  let $x-names := $x[1]/ancestor-or-self::element()/name(),
      $y-names := $y[1]/ancestor-or-self::element()/name()

  return count($x-names) + count($y-names) + 1
        - 2*count( for $x-name at $x-pos in $x-names
                  where $x-name eq $y-names[$x-pos] return 1)
        + ( if ( ( count($x-names) eq count($y-names) )
              and $x/name() eq $y/name() ) then 2 else 0 )
};
```

As regards the implementation of the `sp-dist()` function, the use of the `ancestor-or-self` is again proposed. Furthermore, the `name()` XQuery function is used in order to retrieve the list of the qualified names of the nodes in the two paths starting from the root and up to the considered elements. Starting from the root up to the last element of the shortest list, we perform a memberwise comparison between the corresponding elements (i.e., the first element of $\$x$ with the first element of $\$y$, the second element of $\$x$ with the second element of $\$y$ and so on). Considering the common elements of the two lists, the function `sp-dist()` can compute the shortest distance between $\$x$ and $\$y$ (see Listing 2).

As regards the inter-evaluation relationship, it can be enforced by generating an ordered stream of tuples of variables bound to the parents of the elements associated to an elementary criterion of satisfaction. During the generation of these tuples, the ancestor relationship can also be enforced by checking whether the distance amongst the related bound variables is equal to the shortest distance.

Finally, when valid tuples respecting both ancestor and inter-evaluation relationships are generated in the context of the XQuery `for` clause, the intra-evaluation relationship can be evaluated within each elementary criterion of satisfaction. This can be done by considering that the bound variables generated by the `for` clause refer to the parent nodes of the elements under evaluation.

After having generated the valid tuples of attribute values, the elementary criteria of satisfaction can be evaluated. It is selected to adopt user-defined functions and prototype implementations are proposed in Appendix 13 (see `xm:linearIncrement`, `xm:linearDecrement`,

Figure 3. Tree view of the XML document (in each node, the left symbol is the element QName and the symbol is the value element value)

`xm:linearWithAround`, `xm:linearNotAround`, `xm:simpleEnumD`, `xm:simpleEnumS`). In the case of a relative ranking, it is proposed to compute the aggregated value and bind it to a variable before starting the tuples generation.

After the evaluation of the elementary criteria of satisfaction for each valid tuple of attribute values, the overall satisfaction can be computed taking into account the classification by relevance expressed by the `XMWhereClause`. In order to perform this task, a generic user-defined function is proposed that accepts as input arguments three sequences, each of them composed by the elementary satisfactions in a certain relevance class (see function `xm:globalScore` in Appendix 13).

Given the overall satisfaction for each valid tuple of attribute values, the solution (`XMReturnClause`) is built where the results are ordered by their global satisfaction using a decreasing criterion. The 'Top K' results are returned with an optional cut on the minimum threshold. This can be implemented by adding an external `For-Return XQuery` clause.

The proposed solution complies with the XQuery standard, therefore it is portable as regards standard-compliant implementations of the available processors. The only processor-specific dependency is the power function. Such a function has been wrapped in `xm:pow` (see Appendix 13). The mapping proposal described in this section covers all possible use cases with the following restrictions: (1) elements that are associated to an elementary criterion of satisfaction may not be present in the input XML document, nevertheless their parents must exist; (2) the elementary criterion of satisfaction by enumeration supports only the `XMatch eq` comparison predicate on simple elements. A lexical analyzer and a parser reading `XMatch` queries and transforming them into XQuery expressions have been developed by means of Lex and Yacc programs [LS75, Joh75].

2 A Complete Example

In this section, a complete example is presented where an `XMatch` query is mapped into an equivalent XQuery expression according to the proposal given in Section 1. After that, the rewritten query is given as input to an XQuery processor and the results are described. The query engine adopted to perform the experiment is Saxon-B, a Java-based open source XQuery and XSLT processor [Sax06].

In Example 24, the `XMatch` query expressing the user satisfactions to be evaluated on the XML document visualized as a tree in Figure 3 is presented. The query selects a tuple of two elements, A and M, each of them having properties distinguished as essential, desirable and optional as regards their relevance.

Table 1. Elementary satisfactions and overall score

Solution	E	ess			des			opt e4
		e1	e2	e5	e3	e6	e7	
F(3),D(3),E(2),H(7,9),O(7),Q(8),R(9,4)	0.897	1	0.778	0.8	0.111	0.2	1	0.833
F(3),D(3),E(2),H(2,3),O(7),Q(8),R(9,4)	0.889	1	0.778	0.8	0.111	0.2	1	0
F(6),D(3,10),E(28),H(),O(7),Q(8),R(9,4)	0.833	0.6	0.778	0.8	1	0.2	1	0
F(3),D(3),E(2),H(7,9),O(6),Q(5),R(2,7)	0.809	1	0.778	0.6	0.111	0	0	0.833
F(3),D(3),E(2),H(2,3),O(6),Q(5),R(2,7)	0.809	1	0.778	0.6	0.111	0	0	0
F(6),D(3,10),E(28),H(),O(6),Q(5),R(2,7)	0.745	0.6	0.778	0.6	1	0	0	0
F(3),D(9),E(5),H(),O(7),Q(8),R(9,4)	0.564	1	0.111	0.8	0.444	0.2	1	0
F(3),D(9),E(5),H(),O(6),Q(5),R(2,7)	0.489	1	0.111	0.6	0.444	0	0	0

Example 24

```

for $A in doc("data.xml")/T/A, $M in doc("data.xml")/T/M
let $e1 := $A/B/F eq 3 satisfies 1, 6 satisfies 0.6
let $e2 := $A/B/C/D in 1 to 10 satisfies with linear decrement
let $e3 := $A/B/C/E in 1 to 10 satisfies with linear increment
let $e4 := $A/B/C/G/H in 4 to 10 satisfies with linear increment
let $e5 := $M/N/O in 3 to 8 satisfies with linear increment
let $e6 := $M/N/P/Q eq 3 satisfies 0.5, 4 satisfies 0.7, 8 satisfies 0.2
let $e7 := $M/N/P/R eq max satisfies 1 where ($e1, $e2, $e5) are essential
and ($e3,$e6,$e7) are desirable and $e4 is optional
return top 10 with threshold 0.4

```

The generated tuples, the elementary satisfactions and the overall score are presented in Table 1. All generated tuples that are valid solutions are included in the final result because their number is lower than 10 and the minimum threshold is greater than the one specified in the return clause. The presented XMatch query can be mapped into XQuery as defined in Example 25 following the proposed approach.

Example 25

```

import module namespace xm = "http://xmatch.net/xmatch" at "modxmatch.xq";
<results> {
let $maxR := max( let $maxR-Set := doc("test.xml")/T/M/N/P/R return $maxR-Set)
for $top-i at $top-i-pos in
for $A in doc("test.xml")/T/A, $M in doc("test.xml")/T/M,
  $o1 in $A/B,
  $o2 in $A/B/C[xm:dist($o1,.) eq xm:sp-dist($o1,.)],
  $o3 in $A/B/C/G[xm:dist($o2,.) eq xm:sp-dist($o2,.)],
  $o4 in $M/N,
  $o5 in $M/N/P[xm:dist($o4,.) eq xm:sp-dist($o4,.)]
let $e1 := xm:simpleEnumD($o1/F, (3,6), (1,0.6)),
  $e2 := xm:linearDecrement(min($o2/D), 1, 10),
  $e3 := xm:linearIncrement(max($o2/E), 1, 10),
  $e4 := xm:linearIncrement(max($o3/H), 4, 10),
  $e5 := xm:linearIncrement(max($o4/O), 3, 8),
  $e6 := xm:simpleEnumD($o5/Q, (3,4,8), (0.5,0.7,0.2)),
  $e7 := if (max($o5/R) eq $maxR) then 1 else 0,
  $E := xm:globalScore( ($e1,$e2,$e5), ($e3,$e6,$e7), $e4)
where $E >= 0.4 order by $E descending
return <result E="{ $E }">{$A}{$M}</result>
where $top-i-pos <= 10 return $top-i
} </results>

```

In this example, we can see how the overall score is affected with a different relevance by the different classes of attributes. It is also worth noting how the intra-evaluation, inter-evaluation and ancestor relationships effectively only enable the creation of valid solutions amongst the possible combinations of nodes. In particular, sibling nodes having the same qualified names are considered as alternatives and this is also enforced for complex elements (e.g., B). This means that the satisfaction given by a complex element must be considered together with the satisfactions given by its descendants (e.g., there is no tuple having the elements /T/A[1]/B[1]/F[1] and /T/A[1]/B[2]/C[1]/D/[1]).

3 Summary

This chapter presented an approach to rewrite XMatch queries in terms of XQuery. The choices made to map the language construct and its properties were detailed. A complete example was provided together with the experimental results. The proposed solution enables to run XMatch queries using the available XQuery engines.

Conclusion

This thesis has focused on the problem of service selection in Grid systems. Issues such the potentially high number of similar resources and the diversity of perceived user satisfaction were explored. By decomposing the problem in the capability of rigorously representing service characteristics, capability for users to express their expectations flexibly and capability of measuring the degree to which the characteristics fulfill user requirements, the inner concept of quality measurement as defined by the ISO was identified.

The problem was solved by defining a method for selecting Grid services based on the degree to which their characteristics fulfill the user requirements, i.e., based on their quality as regards user expectations. This method was also mapped into a concrete level where resources can be represented by XML documents and users express their needs using the proposed XMatch language.

Summary of Contributions

The first original contribution is a method for selecting Grid services based on the quality requirements expressed by the user. The method consists of two main phases: (1) the planning phase where the domain of interest is rigorously modelled, the relevant attributes (inherent characteristics) are identified, measurements method are defined and an analysis method producing quality indicators is proposed; (2) an execution phase where the measures of attributes are performed (objective measures), the user expresses his or her expectations (requirements, subjective measures) and selection based on quality indicators takes place (degree of satisfaction).

The second original contribution is a mapping of the proposed method into a concrete level. In particular, XMatch is proposed, a high-level query language that natively supports the constructs for expressing elementary satisfactions as regards attribute values and their relevance as defined in the proposed method. The language is inspired by the XQuery language and enables the analysis of the quality indicator over XML-based representations of Grid resources, thus returning those that maximize the satisfaction. A description of a rewriting approach to translate XMatch into XQuery expressions is also provided together with a reference implementation demonstrating its capabilities and functionality.

Future Work

There are many aspects to be considered in the evolution of this work. Amongst them, the following are reputed to be the more relevant: the theoretical model could be extended in order to consider cost-decision models supported in the LSP method; the stated properties of the XMatch language could be formalized in terms of an algebra for XML; the experimental part concerning the proposed mapping into the XQuery language could focus on the analysis of both benefits and performance issues in real scenarios; finally, the prototyping of a native XMatch engine considering optimization aspects specific to this language could be achieved.

Chapter 12

XMatch Grammar

In this appendix, we define the complete grammar of the XMatch language specified in the simple Extended Backus-Naur Form (EBNF). The grammar rules are given only for symbols starting with the prefix XM, whilst the other symbols are taken from the XQuery W3C specification [BCF⁺05].

Grammar 1

```
XMExpr ::= XMForClause XMLetClause+ XMWhereClause XMReturnClause
XMForClause ::= "for" "$" VarName "in" XMDocCall ( "," "$" VarName "in" XMDocCall )*
XMDocCall ::= "doc(" URILiteral ")" XPathExpr? XMPredicate?
XMPredicate ::= "[" OrExpr "]"
XMLetClause ::= "let" ( "$" VarName "!=" ( XMSimpleEnum | XMCompEnum | XMRange ) )
XMSimpleEnum ::= XPathExpr ValueComp XMLElement "satisfies" XMSatLiteral
               ( "," XMLElement "satisfies" XMSatLiteral )*
XMCompEnum ::= XPathExprList ValueComp XMLElementList "satisfies" XMSatLiteral
              ( "," XMLElementList "satisfies" XMSatLiteral )*
XMRange ::= XPathExpr "in" XMLElement "to" XMLElement "satisfies"
           ( "with" "linear" "increment" | "with" "linear" "decrement"
             | "with" "around" | "not" "around" )
XPathExprList ::= "(" XPathExpr ( "," XPathExpr )+ ")"
XMLElementList ::= "(" XMLElement ( "," XMLElement )+ ")"
XMLElement ::= ( XMLiteral | XPathExpr | XMAggregation )
XMLiteral ::= ( XMSatLiteral | XMNumLiteral | StringLiteral )
XMAggregation ::= ( "max" | "min" | "avg" | "sum" | "count" )
XPathExpr ::= ( "/" QName )* ( "/" "@" QName )?
XMWhereClause ::= "where"
                ( ( XMRelevanceSubj ( "essential" | "desirable" | "optional" ) ) |
                  ( XMRelevanceSubj "essential" and XMRelevanceSubj "desirable" ) |
                  ( XMRelevanceSubj "essential" and XMRelevanceSubj "optional" ) |
                  ( XMRelevanceSubj "desirable" and XMRelevanceSubj "optional" ) |
                  ( XMRelevanceSubj "essential" and XMRelevanceSubj "desirable"
                    and XMRelevanceSubj "optional" ) )
XMRelevanceSubj ::= ( "$" VarName "is" | XMVarNameList "are" )
XMVarNameList ::= ( "$" VarName ( "," "$" VarName )+ )
XMReturnClause ::= "return" "top" digits ( "with threshold" XMSatLiteral )?
XMSatLiteral ::= ( "0"? "." Digits | "1" )
XMNumLiteral ::= ( "+" | "-" )? ( [2-9]+ ( "." Digits )? | Digits [0-9] ( "." Digits )? )
```

Chapter 13

XQuery Functions Module

This appendix contains the definition of a library module in the XQuery language. This module provides the implementations of functions needed for the evaluation of an XQuery expression resulting from a mapping of XMatch as described in this work.

Listing 3

```
module namespace xm="http://xmatch.net/xmatch";

(: start code XQuery engine specific                               :)
(: in this example, we use Saxon: http://www.saxonica.com/ :)
declare namespace math = "java:java.lang.Math";
declare function xm:pow($b as xs:double, $e as xs:double) as xs:double {
  math:pow($b, $e)
};
(: end code XQuery engine-specific :)

declare function xm:linearIncrement($x as xs:double?, $x0 as xs:double, $x1 as xs:double)
  as xs:double {
  if ( fn:empty($x) ) then 0
  else if ($x <= $x0) then 0
  else if ($x >= $x1) then 1
  else (($x - $x0) div ($x1 - $x0))
};

declare function xm:linearDecrement($x as xs:double?, $x0 as xs:double, $x1 as xs:double)
  as xs:double {

  if ( fn:empty($x) ) then 0
  else if ($x <= $x0) then 1
  else if ($x >= $x1) then 0
  else (($x1 - $x) div ($x1 - $x0))
};

declare function xm:simpleEnumD($x as xs:double*, $attrs as xs:double*,
  $sats as xs:double*) as xs:double {
  (: to be extended to support all the aggregation functions :)
  (: "eq" | "ne" | "lt" | "le" | "gt" | "ge" :)

  let $matched-sats := for $x-elem in $x
    let $attr-pos := index-of($attrs, $x-elem),
    $sat := if ( fn:exists($attr-pos) )
      then $sats[$attr-pos] else 0
    return $sat
  return if (exists($matched-sats)) then max($matched-sats) else 0
};

declare function xm:simpleEnumS($x as xdt:string*, $attrs as xdt:string*,
  $sats as xs:double*) as xs:double {
  (: to be extended to support all the aggregation functions :)
  (: "eq" | "ne" | "lt" | "le" | "gt" | "ge" :)
  let $matched-sats := for $x-elem in $x
    let $attr-pos := index-of($attrs, $x-elem),
    $sat := if ( fn:exists($attr-pos) )
      then $sats[$attr-pos] else 0
    return $sat
  return if (exists($matched-sats)) then max($matched-sats) else 0
};
```

```

declare function xm:globalScore($ess as xs:double*, $des as xs:double*,
    $opt as xs:double*) as xs:double {

    let $w1 := 0.3, $w2 := 0.8, $w3 := 0.8, $w4 := 0.4, $r := -0.72,
    $ess-num := fn:count($ess), $des-num := fn:count($des), $opt-num := fn:count($opt),
    $ess-pow := if ( $des-num > 1 and $des-num < 6 )
        then (-0.72, -0.73, -0.71, -0.67)[$des-num - 1]
        else 1, (:CA:)
    $des-pow := if ( $des-num > 1 and $des-num < 6 )
        then (-0.26, -0.20, -0.17, -0.16)[$des-num - 1]
        else 1, (:C-)
    $opt-pow := 1,
    $E-ess := if ( $ess-num eq 0 ) then 0
        else if ( $ess-num eq 1 ) then $ess
        else let $e-ess := for $a-ess in $ess
            return ( 1. div $ess-num ) * xm:pow($a-ess, $ess-pow)
        return xm:pow( sum($e-ess), (1. div $ess-pow) ),
    $E-des := if ( $des-num eq 0 ) then 0
        else if ( $des-num eq 1 ) then $des
        else let $e-des := for $a-des in $des
            return ( 1. div $des-num ) * xm:pow($a-des, $des-pow)
        return xm:pow( sum($e-des), (1. div $des-pow) ),
    $E-opt := if ( $opt-num eq 0 ) then 0 else avg($opt),
    $E1 := (1-$w1) * $E-opt + $w1 * $E-des,
    $E2 := xm:pow( (1-$w2) * xm:pow($E1,$r) + $w2 * xm:pow($E-des,$r), $r),
    $E3 := (1-$w3) * $E2 + $w3 * $E-ess,
    $E := xm:pow( (1-$w4) * xm:pow($E3,$r) + $w4 * xm:pow($E-ess,$r), $r)
    return $E
};

declare function xm:linearAround($x as xs:double*, $x0 as xs:double, $x1 as xs:double)
    as xs:double {
    fn:max( for $z in $x
        let $y := if ( ($z <= $x0) or ($z >= $x1) ) then 0
            else if ( $z <= ($x0 + (($x1 - $x0) div 2) )
                then (($z - $x0) div (($x1 - $x0) div 2) )
            else (($x1 - $z) div (($x1 - $x0) div 2) )
        return $y)
};

declare function xm:linearNotAround($x as xs:double*, $x0 as xs:double,
    $x1 as xs:double) as xs:double {
    let $value := 1.0 - xm:linearAround($x, $x0, $x1)
    return $value
};

declare function xm:dist($x as node(), $y as node()) as xs:integer {
    let $x-ancestors := $x/ancestor-or-self::element(),
    $y-ancestors := $y/ancestor-or-self::element()
    return count($x-ancestors)+count($y-ancestors)
        +1-2*count($x-ancestors intersect $y-ancestors)
};

declare function xm:sp-dist($x as node(), $y as node()) as xs:integer {
    let $x-names := $x/ancestor-or-self::element()/name(),
    $y-names := $y/ancestor-or-self::element()/name()
    return count($x-names) + count($y-names) + 1 - 2*count(
        for $x-name at $x-pos in $x-names
        where $x-name eq $y-names[$x-pos]
        return 1) + ( if ( ( count($x-names) eq count($y-names) )
            and $x/name() eq $y/name() ) then 2 else 0)
};

```

References

- [AAA⁺04] P. Andreetto, S. Andreatto, G. Avellino, et al. Practical Approaches to Grid Workload and Resource Management in the EGEE Project. In *Proceedings of the Conference on Computing in High Energy and Nuclear Physics (CHEP 2004)*, Interlaken, Switzerland, Sep 2004.
- [AARW⁺02] R.J. Al-Ali, O.F. Rana, D.W. Walker, A. Jha, and S. Sohail. G-QoS: Grid Service Discovery Using QoS Properties. *International Journal of Computing and Informatics*, 21(4):363–382, 2002.
- [ABC⁺04] J. Alexander, D. Box, L.F. Cabrera, D. Chappell, G. Daniels, A. Geller, R. Janecek, C. Kaler, B. Lovering, D. Orchard, J. Schlimmer, I. Sedukhin, and J. Shewchuk. Web Service Transfer (WS-Transfer). <http://msdn.microsoft.com/ws/2004/09/ws-transfer/>, Sep 2004.
- [ABD⁺05] A. Anjomshoaa, F. Brisard, M. Drescher, D. Fellows, A. Ly, S. McGough, D. Pulsipher, and A. Savva. Job Submission Description Language (JSDL) Specification, Version 1.0. GGF GFD.56, Nov 2005.
- [ABF⁺05] S. Andreatto, S. Burke, L. Field, S. Fisher, B. Kónya, M. Mambelli, J.M. Schopf, M. Viljoen, and A. Wilson. GLUE Schema Specification - Version 1.2, Dec 2005.
- [ACd04] S. Andreatto, V. Ciaschini, and L. dell’Agnello. An Abstract Model of the Virtual Organization Membership Service. Technical Report INFN/TC-04/18, INFN, Dec 2004.
- [ACGV04] S. Andreatto, A. Ciuffoletti, A. Ghiselli, and C. Vistoli. Monitoring the Connectivity of a Grid. In *Proceedings of the 2nd International Workshop on Middleware for Grid Computing (MGC 2004)*, Toronto, Canada, Oct 2004.
- [ACMM04a] S. Andreatto, P. Ciancarini, D. Montesi, and R. Moretti. Towards a Metamodeling Based Method for Representing and Selecting Grid Services. In *Proceedings of the 1st International Conference on Grid Services Engineering and Management (GSEM’04)*, Erfurt (Germany), volume 3270 of LNCS. Springer, Oct 2004.
- [ACMM04b] S. Andreatto, P. Ciancarini, D. Montesi, and R. Moretti. Towards a Model for Quality of Web and Grid Services. In *Proceedings of the 13th International Workshops on Enabling Technologies: Infrastructures for Collaborative Enterprises (WETICE-2004)*, Modena, Italy, Jun 2004.
- [ACMM05a] S. Andreatto, P. Ciancarini, D. Montesi, and R. Moretti. An Approach to the Quantitative Evaluation of Grid Services. *Journal of Concurrency and Computation: Practice and Experience*, John Wiley & Sons Ltd., 2005.
- [ACMM05b] S. Andreatto, P. Ciancarini, D. Montesi, and R. Moretti. Towards a Language for a Satisfaction-based Selection of Grid Services. In *Proceedings of the 2nd Grid Resource Management Workshop 2005 (GRMW 2005) in conjunction with the 6th International Conference on Parallel Processing and Applied Mathematics (PPAM 2005)*, Poznań, Poland, volume 3911 of LNCS. Springer, Sep 2005.
- [ADD⁺04] M. Atkinson, D. DeRoure, A. Dunlop, G. Fox, P. Henderson, T. Hey, N. Paton, S. Newhouse, S. Parastatidis, A. Trefethen, P. Watson, and J. Webber. Web Service Grids: An Evolutionary Approach. Technical Report UKeS-2004-05, UK e-Science Institute, 2004.
- [ALI] ALICE-A Large Ion Collider Experiment. <http://www.cern.ch/alice>.

- [AMM03] S. Andreozzi, D. Montesi, and R. Moretti. Web Services Quality. In *Proceedings of the International Conference on Computer, Communication and Control Technologies (CCCT03), Orlando, FL, USA*, pages 252–257, Ago 2003.
- [AMM05] S. Andreozzi, D. Montesi, and R. Moretti. XMatch: a Language for Satisfaction-based Selection of Grid Services. *Scientific Programming Journal, Special Issue on Grids and Worldwide Computing, IOS Press*, 13(4):299–316, 2005.
- [ATL] ATLAS (A Toroidal LHC Apparatus). <http://www.cern.ch/atlas>.
- [BBC⁺05a] A. Berglund, S. Boag, D Chamberlin, M.F. Fernández, M. Kay, J. Robie, and J. Siméon. XML Path Language (XPath) 2.0. W3C Candidate Recommendation, Nov 2005.
- [BBC⁺05b] R. Bilorusets, D. Box, L.F. Cabrera, D. Davis, D. Ferguson, C. others Ferris, T. Freund, M.A. Hondo, J. Ibbotson, L. Jin, C. Kaler, D. Langworthy, A. Lewis, R. Limprecht, S. Lucco, D. Mullen, A. Nadalin, A. Nottingham, D. Orchard, J. Roots, S. Samdarshi, J. Shewchuk, and T. Storey. Web Services Reliable Messaging Protocol (WS-ReliableMessaging). <http://www-128.ibm.com/developerworks/library/specification/ws-rm/>, Feb 2005.
- [BCC⁺04] D. Box, L.F. Cabrera, C. Critchley, F. Curbera, D. Ferguson, A. Geller, S. Graham, D. Hull, G. Kakivaya, A. Lewis, B. Lovering, M. Mihic, P. Niblett, D. Orchard, J. Saiyed, S. Samdarshi, J. Schlimmer, I. Sedukhin, J. Shewchuk, B. Smith, S. Weerawarana, and D. Wortendyke. Web Services Eventing (WS-Eventing). <http://www-128.ibm.com/developerworks/library/specification/ws-eventing/>, Aug 2004.
- [BCF⁺05] S. Boag, D Chamberlin, M.F. Fernández, D Florescu, J. Robie, and J. Simeon. XQuery 1.0: An XML Query Language. W3C Candidate Recommendation, Nov 2005.
- [Bec04] D. Beckett. RDF/XML Syntax Specification (Revised). W3C Recommendation, Feb 2004.
- [BEF⁺00] R. Butler, D. Engert, I. Foster, C. Kesselman, S. Tuecke, J. Volmer, and V. Welch. A National-Scale Authentication Infrastructure. *IEEE Computer*, 33(12):60–66, 2000.
- [BEF⁺04] K. Ballinger, D. Ehnebuske, C. Ferris, M. Gudgin, C. Kevin Liu, M. Nottingham, and P. Yendluri. WS-I Basic Profile version 1.1. WS-I Organization Final Material, Ago 2004.
- [BHM⁺04] D. Booth, H. Haas, F. McCabe, E. Newcomer, M. Champion, C. Ferris, and D. Orchard. Web Services Architecture. W3C Working Group Note, Feb 2004.
- [BPE] OASIS Web Services Business Process Execution Language (WSBPEL) Technical Committee. <http://www.oasis-open.org/committees/wsbpel>.
- [Bul03] P.S. Bullen. *Handbook of Means and Their Inequalities*. Kluwer Academic Publishers, second edition, 2003.
- [CCMW01] E. Christensen, F. Curbera, G. Meredith, and S. Weerawarana. Web Services Description Language (WSDL) 1.1. W3C Note, Mar 2001.
- [CER] CERN, the European Organization for Nuclear Research. <http://www.cern.ch>.
- [CFF⁺04] K. Czajkowski, D.F. Ferguson, I. Foster, J. Frey, S. Graham, I. Sedukhin, D. Snelling, S. Tuecke, W. Vambenepe, and S. Weerawarana. The WS-Resource Framework, version 1.0. White Paper, Mar 2004.

- [CFFK01] K. Czajkowski, S. Fitzgerald, I. Foster, and C. Kesselman. Grid Information Services for Distributed Resource Sharing. In *Proceedings of the 10th IEEE International Symposium on High-Performance Distributed Computing (HPDC-10)*, Aug 6-9, San Francisco, CA, USA, 2001.
- [CGN⁺04] A.W. Cooke, A.J.G. Gray, Werner Nutt, J. Magowan, M. Oevers, P. Taylor, R. Cordeonensi, R. Byrom, L. Cornwall, A. Djaoui, L. Field, S. Fisher, S. Hicks, S. Leake, R. Middleton, A.J. Wilson, X. Zhu, N. Podhorszki, B.A. Coghlan, S. Kenny, D. O'Callaghan, and J. Ryan. The Relational Grid Monitoring Architecture: Mediating Information about the Grid. *Journal of Grid Computing*, Springer, 2(4):323–339, 2004.
- [Cho03] J. Chomicki. Preference Formulas in Relational Queries. *ACM Transaction on Database Systems*, 28(4):427–466, 2003.
- [CMS] CMS (Compact Muon Solenoid). <http://www.cern.ch>.
- [DF04a] J.J. Dujmovic and W.Y. Fang. An Empirical Analysis of Assessment Errors for Weights and Andness in LSP Criteria. In *Proceedings of the International Conference on Modeling Decisions for Artificial Intelligence (MDAI2004)*, Barcelona, Spain, volume 3131 of LNCS/LNAI. Springer, Aug 2004.
- [DF04b] J.J. Dujmovic and W.Y. Fang. Reliability of LSP Criteria. In *Proceedings of the International Conference on Modeling Decisions for Artificial Intelligence (MDAI2004)*, Barcelona, Spain, volume 3131 of LNCS/LNAI. Springer, Aug 2004.
- [DKP⁺99] H. Davulcu, M. Kifer, L.R. Pokorny, C.R. Ramakrishnan, I.V. Ramakrishnan, and S. Dawson. Modeling and Analysis of Interactions in Virtual Enterprises. In *Proceedings of the 9th International Workshop on Research Issues on Data Engineering (RIDE1999) Information Technology for Virtual Enterprises*, Seattle, WA, Nov 1999.
- [DS04] K. Dean and T. Solomonides. HealthGrid - a Summary. Cisco White Paper, <http://whitepaper.healthgrid.org>, Nov 2004.
- [Duj96] J.J. Dujmovic. A Method for Evaluation and Selection of Complex Hardware and Software Systems. In *Proceedings of the International Conference for the Resource Management and Performance Evaluation of Enterprise Computing Systems (CMG96)*, San Diego, CA, USA, volume 1, pages 368–378, Dec 1996.
- [Duj05] J.J. Dujmovic. Continuous Preference Logic for System Evaluation. In *Proceedings of the Eurofuse Workshop (EUROFUSE2005)*, Belgrade, Serbia and Montenegro, Jun 2005.
- [FBA⁺05] I. Foster, D. Berry, Djaoui. A., A. Grimshaw, B. Horn, H. Kishimoto, F. Maciel, A. Savva, F. Siebenlist, R. Subramaniam, J. Treadwell, and J. Von Reich. The Open Grid Services Architecture (OGSA), version 1.0. GGF GFD.30, Jan 2005.
- [FBA⁺06] I. Foster, D. Berry, Djaoui. A., A. Grimshaw, B. Horn, H. Kishimoto, F. Maciel, A. Savva, F. Siebenlist, R. Subramaniam, J. Treadwell, and J. Von Reich. The Open Grid Services Architecture (OGSA), version 1.5. GGF Working Draft 8, Mar 2006.
- [FGE05] J. Figueira, S. Greco, and M. Ehrgott, editors. *Multiple Criteria Decision Analysis: State of the Art Surveys*. Springer, 2005.
- [Fie00] R.T. Fielding. *Architectural Styles and the Design of Network-based Software Architectures*. PhD thesis, University of California, Irvine, CA, USA, 2000.
- [FKNT02] I. Foster, C. Kesselman, J. Nick, and S. Tuecke. The Physiology of the Grid: an Open Grid Services Architecture for Distributed systems Integration. <http://www.globus.org/alliance/publications/papers/ogsa.pdf>, Jun 2002.

- [FKT01] I. Foster, C. Kesselman, and S. Tuecke. The Anatomy of the Grid: Enabling Scalable Virtual Organizations. *International Journal of High Performance Computing Applications*, 15(3):200–222, 2001.
- [FKTT98] I. Foster, C. Kesselman, G. Tsudik, and S. Tuecke. A Security Architecture for Computational Grids. In *Proceedings of the 5th ACM Conference on Computer and Communications Security Conference (CCS5), San Francisco, CA, USA*, pages 83–92, 1998.
- [FMM⁺05] M. Fernández, A. Malhotra, J. Marsh, M. Nagy, and N. Walsh. XQuery 1.0 and XPath 2.0 Data Model. W3C Candidate Recommendation, Nov 2005.
- [For03] Distributed Management Task Force. CIM Concepts. DMTF White Paper DSP0110, Jun 2003.
- [FS98] N.E. Fenton and Pfleeger S.L. *Software Metrics: a Rigorous and Practical Approach, 2nd edition*. Course Technology, 1998.
- [GGF] Global Grid Forum. <http://www.ggf.org>.
- [GH05] M. Gudgin and M. Hadley. Web Services Addressing 1.0 - Core. W3C Candidate Recommendation, Aug 2005.
- [GHM05] S. Graham, D. Hull, and B. Murray. Web Services Base Notification 1.3 (WS-BaseNotification). OASIS Public Review - Draft 2, Nov 2005.
- [GLO] The Globus Alliance. <http://www.globus.org>.
- [GT06] S. Graham and J. Treadwell. Web Services Resource Properties 1.2 (WS-ResourceProperties). OASIS Committee Specification, Jan 2006.
- [HFPS99] R. Housley, W. Ford, W. Polk, and D. Solo. Internet X.509 Public Key Infrastructure Certificate and CRL Profile. IETF RFC 459, 1999.
- [HK05] B. Hafenrichter and W. Kießling. Optimization of Relational Preference Queries. In *Proceedings of the 16th Australasian Database (ADB05) Conference, Newcastle, Australia, 2005*.
- [HWK⁺05] M. Humphrey, G. Wasson, Y. Kiryakov, S.M. Park, D. Del Vecchio, and N. Beekwilder. Alternative Software Stacks for OGSA-based Grids. In *Proceedings of Supercomputing 2005, Seattle, WA, Nov 2005*.
- [Int00] International Standard Organization. ISO 9000:2000 Quality Management Systems - Fundamentals and Vocabulary, 2000.
- [Joh75] S.C. Johnson. Yacc: Yet Another Compiler Compiler. Technical Report 32, Bell Laboratories, Murray Hill, New Jersey, USA, 1975.
- [JW04] I. Jacobs and N. Walsh. Architecture of the World Wide Web. W3C Recommendation, Dec 2004.
- [KHFH01] W. Kießling, B. Hafenrichter, S. Fischer, and S. Holland. Preference XPATH: a Query Language for E-Commerce. In *Proceedings of 5th Internationale Tagung Wirtschaftsinformatik, Augsburg, Germany, Sep 2001*.
- [Kie02] W. Kießling. Foundations of Preferences in Database Systems. In *Proceedings of the 28th Very Large Database System (VLDB) Conference, Hong Kong, China, Aug 2002*.
- [KK02] W. Kießling and G. Köstler. Preference SQL - Design, Implementation, Experiences. In *Proceedings of 28th International Conference on Very Large Databases (VLDB), Hong Kong, China, Aug 2002*.

- [KNOW03] K. Kurowski, J. Nabrzyski, A. Oleksiak, and J. Weglarz. *Grid Resource Management : State of the Art and Future Trends*, chapter Multicriteria Aspects of Grid Resource Management, pages 271–293. Springer, 2003.
- [KT05] H. Kishimoto and J. Treadwell. Defining the Grid: a Roadmap for OGSA Standards - Version 1.0. GGF GFD.53, Sep 2005.
- [LAWG05] P. Lord, P. Alper, C. Wroe, and C. Goble. Feta: a Light-Weight Architecture for User Oriented Semantic Service Discovery. In *Proceedings of 2nd European Semantic Web Conference (ESWC 2005), Heraklion, Crete, Greece*, volume 3532 of LNCS. Springer, May 2005.
- [LCB⁺04] M. Lorch, B. Cowles, R. Baker, L. Gommans, P. Madsen, A. McNab, L. Ramakrishnan, K. Sankar, D. Skow, and M.R. and Thompson. Conceptual Grid Authorization Framework and Classification. GGF GFD.38, Nov 2004.
- [LCG] LCH Computing Grid. <http://www.cern.ch/lcg>.
- [LF04] C. Liu and I. Foster. A Constraint Language Approach to Matchmaking. In *Proceedings of the International workshop on Research Issues on Data Engineering (RIDE 2004), Boston*, 2004.
- [LHC] LHC-B (LHC - Beauty). <http://www.cern.ch>.
- [LLM88] M. Litzkow, M. Livny, and M. W. Mutka. Condor - a Hunter of Idle Workstations. In *Proceedings of the 8th International Conference on Distributed Computing Systems (ICDCS 1988), San Jose, CA, USA*, Jun 1988.
- [LLM03] M. J. Litzkow, M. Livny, and M. W. Mutka. Policy Driven Heterogeneous Resource Co-Allocation with Gangmatching. In *Proceedings of the 12th IEEE International Symposium on High-Performance Distributed Computing (HPDC 2003), Seattle, WA, USA*, Jun 2003.
- [LM06] L. Liu and S. Meder. Web Services Base Faults 1.2 (WS-BaseFaults). OASIS Committee Specification, Jan 2006.
- [LR05] S. A. Ludwig and S.M.S. Reyhani. Semantic Approach to Service Discovery in a Grid Environment. *Journal of Web Semantics, Elsevier Ltd.*, 3(4), 2005.
- [LS75] M.E. Lesk and E. Schmidt. Lex A Lexical Analyzer Generator. Computing Science 39, Bell Laboratories, Murray Hill, New Jersey, USA, 1975.
- [MBL⁺04] D. Martin, M. Burstein, O. Lassila, M. Paolucci, T. Payne, and S. McIlraith. Describing Web Services using OWL-S and WSDL. DARPA Agent Markup Language Program, 2004.
- [MCJ⁺01] J. McGarry, D. Card, C. Jones, B. Layman, E. Clark, J. Dean, and F. Hall. *Practical Software Measurement: Objective Information for Decision Makers*. Addison-Wesley Professional, 1st edition, 2001.
- [MDS05] Globus Toolkit 4.0: Information Services. <http://www.globus.org/toolkit/docs/4.0/info/>, 2005.
- [Mit03] N. Mitra. SOAP Version 1.2 Part 0: Primer, W3C Recommendation, Jun 2003.
- [My198] J. Mylopoulos. Information Modeling in the Time of the Revolution. *Information Systems, Springer*, 23(3-4):127–155, May-Jun 1998.
- [NS03] Z. Németh and V. Sunderam. Characterizing Grids: Attributes, Definitions, and Formalisms. *Journal of Grid Computing*, 1(1):9–23, 2003.

- [NS06] Z. Németh and V. Sunderam. *Grid Computing: Software Environments and Tools*, chapter Virtualization in Grids: a Semantical Approach. Springer, 2006.
- [OAS] Organization for the Advancement of Structured Information Standards. <http://www.oasis-open.org>.
- [OMI] The Open Middleware Infrastructure Initiative. <http://www.omii.ac.uk>.
- [Sax06] Saxonica Ltd. Saxon-B, an Open Source XSTL and XQuery processor. <http://www.saxonica.com>, 2006.
- [SB06] L. Srinivasan and T. Banks. Web Services Resource Lifetime 1.2 (WS-ResourceLifetime). OASIS Committee Specification, Jan 2006.
- [Sea04] A. Seaborne. RDQL - A Query Language for RDF. W3C Member Submission, Jan 2004.
- [SEG] Semantic Grid. <http://www.semanticgrid.org>.
- [SEW] Semantic Web. <http://www.w3.org/2001/sw>.
- [SF04] E. Stokes and L. Flon. Job Submission Information Model (JSIM) - Version 1.0. GGF GFD.28, May 2004.
- [SJB⁺87] S.W. Su, Dujmovic J.J., D.S. Batory, S.B. Navathe, and R. Elnicki. A Cost-Benefit Decision Model: Analysis, Comparison, and Selection of Data Management Systems. *ACM Transaction on Database Systems*, 12(3):472–520, 1987.
- [Sol03] M. Solomon. *The ClassAd Language Reference Manual, Version 2.1*. Computer Sciences Department, University of Wisconsin, Madison, WI, USA, Oct 2003.
- [SRAAW03] A. ShaikhAli, O.F. Rana, R. Al-Ali, and D.W. Walker. UDDIe: an Extended Registry for Web Services. In *Workshop on Service Oriented Computing: Models, Architectures and Applications at SAINT Conference, Florida, USA*, Jan 2003.
- [TDK03] H. Tangmunarunkit, S. Decker, and C. Kesselman. Ontology-Based Resource Matching in the Grid - The Grid Meets the Semantic Web. In *Proceedings of the 2nd International Semantic Web Conference (ISWC 2003), Sanibel Island, FL, USA*, Oct 2003.
- [TOP] TOP500 Supercomputer Sites. <http://www.top500.org>.
- [Tra97] B. Travica. The Design of the Virtual Organization: a Research Model. In *Proceedings of the Americas Conference on Information Systems (AMCIS 1997), Indianapolis, IN, USA*, Aug 1997.
- [TWE⁺04] S. Tuecke, V. Welch, D. Engert, L. Pearlman, and M. Thompson. Internet X.509 Public Key Infrastructure (PKI) Proxy Certificate Profile. IETF RFC 3820, Jun 2004.
- [UML05] Unified Modeling Language: Superstructure version 2.0. Object Management Group, Aug 2005.
- [VHPSH01] F. Van Harmelen, P.F. Patel-Schneider, and I. Horrocks. Reference Description of the DAML+OIL Ontology Markup Language. DARPA Agent Markup Language Program, 2001.
- [WHK97] M. Wahl, T. Howes, and S. Kille. Lightweight Directory Access Protocol (v3). IETF RFC 2251, Dec 1997.

- [WSF+03] V. Welch, F. Siebenlist, I. Foster, J. Bresnahan, K. Czajkowski, J. Gawor, C. Kesselman, S. Meder, L. Pearlman, and S. Tuecke. Security for Grid Services. In *Proceedings of the 12th IEEE International Symposium on High Performance Distributed Computing (HPDC-12), Seattle, WA, USA, 2003*.
- [WSN] OASIS Web Services Notification (WSN) Technical Committee. <http://www.oasis-open.org/committees/wsn>.
- [WSR] OASIS Web Services Resource Framework (WSRF) Technical Committee. <http://www.oasis-open.org/committees/wsrp>.